

A rapid assessment of the immediate environmental impacts of the destruction of the Nova Kakhovka Dam, Ukraine

UK Centre for
Ecology & Hydrology

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Executive summary

The dam of the Kakhovka hydro power plant, known as the Kakhovka Dam or Nova Kakhovka Dam, near Nova Kakhovka town, Kherson Region, Ukraine, suffered a catastrophic breach on 6 June 2023. In response to this event, the UK Foreign and Commonwealth Development Office commissioned the UK Centre for Ecology & Hydrology and HR Wallingford to conduct a rapid (12 – 26 June 2023) remote, desk-based environmental risk assessment of the flood event and potential impacts on the surrounding environment.

The main objectives of this work are:

- **Component 1:** To assess the flood hydrology, hydraulics and sediment transport following the dam breach
- **Component 2:** To conduct a GIS-based assessment to quantify impacts across key categories (e.g. extent of protected ecosystems, potential pollution sources flooded, proportions of land-use types impacted etc.)
- **Component 3:** To classify hazards informing the development and application of a plausible risk assessment approach across species, habitats and river basin scales
- **Component 4:** To identify potential issues of concern that warrant further assessment beyond the timescales of this project.

Results presented here indicate that the maximum flood extent was around 83,000 hectares (~2.6 times the land area of Malta) with maximum flow speeds on the flood plain of around 1 m/s, and a maximum water depth in the affected urban areas of around 2 m. The faster flow rate downstream of the dam has increased the sediment transport capacity in this segment of the river. It is estimated that the flow conditions generated after dam failure will have mobilised at least fine gravel particles. Four main irrigation canals that were formerly connected to the reservoir are no longer supplied with water, affecting large areas of agriculture.

Over half a million hectares of habitat of national or international conservation importance will have been affected by the dam breach along a continuum from the Kakhovka Reservoir to the Black Sea, exposing 567 European Red List species to a

range of potential hazards, 28 of which are threatened at a European level (vulnerable status or worse, excluding 'regionally extinct', 'extinct in the wild' and 'extinct'). For comparison, Ukraine has 147 globally threatened species whereas the United Kingdom has 200 (IUCN, 2023).

In the upstream Kakhovka Reservoir, significant numbers of fish are likely to have been washed out and stranded. The Ukraine State Fisheries Agency estimate that 28,000 crucian carp were lost following the dam failure; estimates for potential total losses caused the event could reach 95,000 tonnes with a commercial value of USD 108 million for mature fish. Downstream of the dam, freshwater habitats of the Dnipro River will have been subjected to scour, which occurs when water erodes the sediments supporting structures.

Flooding in June is highly likely to have disrupted the life cycles of many freshwater and terrestrial species, including the Dnipro sturgeon and the downstream hatcheries established to support its conservation, as well as other migratory aquatic species. For terrestrial species, direct loss or damage of nests and offspring will have occurred, affecting for example birds nesting on the ground, (e.g. little gull, little bustard) or in emergent vegetation. These examples breed in the affected area and are European Red-listed species, classified as "near threatened" or "vulnerable". Terrestrial habitats in the flooded areas downstream are composed mostly of herbaceous wetlands (around 35,000 ha, 51% of the affected downstream area, ESA WorldCover 2021; Zanaga et al., 2022) in the Dnipro valley and delta. These wetlands are a mosaic of rivers, streams, pools, floodplain forests, swamps, reedbeds and sandbars.

Potential pollution sources which have been flooded include wastewater treatment works, petrol stations, landfills and other industrial infrastructure. Historical pollutants contained within reservoir bed sediments – potentially including mine waste and radioactive substances – along with sediment containing pollutants from the sources above will now have been dispersed across the aforementioned habitats and into the coastal ecosystems of the Black Sea Biosphere Reserve. This Reserve is home to bottlenose dolphin, harbour porpoise, Pontic or Black Sea shad, otters, the Stepp polecat, and the critically endangered slender-billed curlew, numbers of which globally are thought to be less than 50 individuals. The Dnipro delta is important as a staging post for migratory and breeding birds including the near threatened, red-breasted goose. The impacts of the dam breach on many of these species is difficult to determine without on-the-ground surveillance.

The report highlights the importance of international collaboration supporting surveillance and data sharing in producing estimates of environmental impacts of the Nova Kakhovka Dam failure impact with high confidence. We recognise that other international evidence reviews are ongoing into this event. An evidence review on the Kakhovka Dam breach is being led by the United Nations Environment Programme Conflicts and Disasters Branch.

A coordinated international scientific response through bi-lateral knowledge sharing could be explored to increase confidence in impact assessments, including with the Ministry of Environmental Protection and Natural Resources of Ukraine and the United Nations Environment Programme. The response team should be urgently established and tasked with producing:

- A consolidated international evidence review on the impacts of the Kakhovka Dam breach on habitats and biodiversity.
- A disaster recovery road map for the impacted habitats and biodiversity.

General approach and key findings

Flood extent, maximum flow speed and sediment impacts

Component 1 (detailed in Section 2 of this report)

A hydraulic model of the reservoir, dam and downstream reach of the Dnipro River was developed to gain insight into the evolution of the dam breach event, the outflow of water from the reservoir, and the extent, depth, duration and speed of the flood flows across the impacted area downstream. The model results informed the high-level sediment analysis, supplying information on flow volumes, velocities and reservoir drawdown rates, which are important factors affecting the erosion, transportation and deposition of sediment. In turn, the sediment analysis indicated likely reduced storage volumes in the reservoir, due to sedimentation rates since its construction, thereby refining the estimate of outflow volumes that caused the flooding downstream. Key findings were as follows:

C1.1 Hydraulic modelling shows that the maximum flood extent was around 83,000 hectares. The maximum flood extent occurred between day 0 (6 June) and day 3 (9 June), related to the distance downstream of the dam. Peak simulated water depths were up to 2m in the urban areas. The peak of the event was attenuated across a period of about two days at Kherson. Maximum flow speeds on the floodplain reached 1 m/s, with very high flow speeds of greater than 3 m/s simulated in the river channels in the first 15 km downstream of the dam. The flow speeds in the main channel downstream of this tended to be between 1 and 3 m/s. Peak flow speeds occurred during the rising flood wave in the first 36 hours.

C1.2 Based upon analysis of historical floods, it is expected that the flood regime of the Lower Dnipro River without the Nova Kakhovka Dam will not change significantly relative to historical conditions. Flood flows may be slightly higher during medium and small floods, but evidence from the 1970s flood event indicates that conditions in a major flood would be relatively unaffected.

C1.3 Sediment-related impacts downstream of the dam, as a result of the flood caused by the dam breach, include erosion at the toe of infrastructures such as intakes, bank protection, or flood embankments and bridge piers and abutments, due to development of general bed and bank erosion. Increased turbidity of surface water is likely to cause the blockage of light penetration, lowering levels of oxygen in the water, suffocation of aquatic life and an increase in water treatment costs.

C1.4 There is likely to be an increased risk of pollution due to the capacity of the sediments in the reservoir to carry nutrients and chemical contaminants, and as a result of exposure of historically contaminated deeper sediment layers in the reservoir. Likely impacts also include destruction of habitats of stream organisms and changes in the navigation channels.

Spatial analysis of affected habitats, biodiversity and land use

Component 2 (detailed in Section 3 of this report)

A wide range of satellite data were accessed, processed and interpreted to validate the model, as well as contributing key information for the Rapid Environmental Impact Assessment. This exercise assessed impacts upon the agriculture and water supply sectors, in addition to the impacts upon numerous freshwater, terrestrial and coastal habitats in this area of international conservation importance. Key findings included:

C2.1 Using the maximum modelled extent, 62% of the land inundated by the downstream flood from the Kakhovka Dam breach is classified as herbaceous wetland; 5% is classified as built-up land; cropland is less than 2% (at approximately 871 ha). There are additional horticulture installations that may increase the estimates of damage to crops.

C2.2 In total, over 529,000 ha of land and water designated as being of national or international conservation importance (e.g. Ramsar and Emerald Network designation), and with one or more level of environmental protection, has potentially been affected. This includes 138,000 ha downstream of the dam within the pre-flood / flooded water extents, 186,000 ha in nearby coastal areas and 205,000 ha within the pre-flood reservoir.

C2.3 Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) occurrence records from the affected area include 142 species in the Ukrainian Red Books and 567 in the European Red List – with some featuring in both. Of those in the Ukrainian Red Book, 86 (~60%) are classified as vulnerable or worse. In the European Red List this figure is 28 (~5%). Threatened species span all habitats, including terrestrial (e.g. Saker Falcon), freshwater (e.g. Sterlet), semi-aquatic (e.g. European mink) and marine (e.g. Harbour porpoise).

C2.4 Within the modelled maximum flood extent, the collated pollution source dataset - compiled from open data - identified 1,087 features in eight potential pollution categories, with a total area of 'hazardous land' of ~4,300 ha.

C2.5 The entrances to the irrigation canals on the Kakhovka Reservoir are visibly above the water level and the canals are drying out. The canal on the north bank near Maryanske is also understood to be for irrigation water supply and is also likely to be dry.

Assessment of hazards and risks across areas of high conservation importance

Component 3 (detailed in Section 4 of this report)

Hazard classification was conducted following the Framework proposed by the UN Office for Disaster Risk Reduction (UNDRR & ISC, 2020). The likely severity of impact of each hazard was assessed using reported information and knowledge of the location of the flood extent and flow dynamics, and key infrastructure within the affected regions against expert knowledge of the ecologies of the receiving ecosystems and their sensitivities to each hazard.

C3.1 21 habitat areas were identified to be at risk from 15 hazard types covering the following categories: biological, chemical, environmental, meteorological, hydrological, and geohazards. Analysis showed that no habitat was vulnerable to all hazards, but eight were affected by 10 or more hazards.

C3.2 The main impacts identified were through the mobilisation and transport of nutrients and pollutants, physical transformation of the river network, reservoir water level reduction, and catastrophic downstream flooding and inundation of Protected Areas.

C3.3 Upstream of the breach, the most severely rated hazards were for the 11 habitats affected by the rapid water level reduction (stranding and loss of organisms, habitat drying) and for the reservoir itself which has reduced in volume to become essentially a river.

C3.4 Downstream of the reservoir, 10 habitats were identified to be at 'moderate' to 'severe' risk of organism loss, inundation, and the erosion and deposition of contaminated sediments. These factors relate to the initial force of the flood waters and the subsequent deposition of materials on the inundated land.

Potential issues of concern that warrant further assessment

Component 4 (detailed in Section 5 of this report)

Potential issues of concern for future assessment were identified following a review of reports in the media and following consultation with experts at UKCEH and HRW. The key findings are as follows:

C4.1 Potential impacts have been identified relating to pollutant hazards. These include assessing sources of radioactive contaminants and munitions wastes and their transport down the Dnipro River to the Black Sea. Identifying zones of accumulation for these contaminants and others will aid in post-disaster clean-up efforts. These may, for example, target reducing human health risks associated with consumption of contaminated fish and shellfish, and / or crops.

C4.2 The potential for the destruction of upstream dams and other large dams in eastern Ukraine requires further assessment to inform disaster risk reduction planning following the approaches developed here. Five dams remain on the Dnipro River cascade above Kakhovka. This should include an assessment of flood risk to the Zaporizhzhia Nuclear Powerplant associated with a failure of the upstream Dnipro Dam.

C4.3 Hydrological impacts that are likely to inform post-conflict reconstruction planning were identified. Alterations in the hydrological regime at this scale will have impacted water infrastructure and quality, affecting drinking water supply and irrigation for agriculture. Seasonal flood extents may be altered, impacting shoreline development and sediment transport; and alterations to river/coastal bed morphology (and dispersal of unexploded munitions) in the lower Dnipro River network may impact navigation. This system represents a key artery of the global grain shipping route.

C4.4 The destruction of habitat caused by the flood will have impacted highly sensitive species of international conservation importance (e.g. the Dnipro sturgeon). The construction of habitat recovery plans to support species of high conservation, cultural, and commercial interest should be developed rapidly. An international response may be required to develop and deliver rapid biodiversity and habitat surveillance and recovery plans.

1.0 Introduction

The Nova Kakhovka Dam was constructed in 1956, forming the Kakhovka Reservoir. The reservoir performed several functions including hydro-electric power generation, and the provision of cooling water to a nuclear power station, irrigation water for agriculture, and drinking water for surrounding human settlements. It was the final and sixth dam along a cascade of regulated systems that control the flow of water along the Dnipro River, as it flows south to the Black Sea. The Dnipro is the largest of Ukraine's nine river basins covering some 65% of the country's entire drainage basin. The Dnipro River is a major transboundary river with headwaters near Smolensk, Russia, and flowing through Belarus, before entering Ukraine on its journey to the Black Sea. The Kakhovka Hydro-electric Power Plant is situated in the town of Nova Kakhovka, Kherson Region, Ukraine.

The region downstream of the Nova Kakhovka Dam is an area of international conservation importance. Numerous freshwater, terrestrial and coastal habitats in the Dnipro River basin have international designations for biodiversity including Ramsar sites and Emerald Network of Areas of Special Conservation Interest.

Reports of a failure of the Nova Kakhovka Dam face initiated on 6 June 2023 and are evident in long-term monitoring data on water levels in the Kakhovka Reservoir (Figure 1.1). This failure has the potential to cause environmental impacts over the flood impact zone. For example, the sudden release of the water may physically destroy protected habitats and organisms, but also transport pollutants from myriad urban and rural infrastructure facilities within the flood impact zone and disrupt irrigation through the large network of canals that support downstream agriculture. There may also be impacts in relation to the wider marine environment.

Fig. 1.1. Depth gauging data (m) for Kakhovka Reservoir from 2016 until 9 June 2023.
Source: https://hydroweb.theia-land.fr/hydroweb/view/L_kakhovka?lang=en&basin=DNIEPR

With the exception of the flood extent, which was informed in the days following 6 June 2023 by analysis of satellite data, the extent and modes of wider impacts on infrastructure and the environment remained unclear. The specific nature of the hydrology of the flood event also required assessment to inform analysis of environmental impact. Hampering these tasks was the difficulty in conducting disaster response surveillance of hazards, and gathering evidence of habitat and biodiversity impacts, within an active combat zone. Finally, a lack of a systematic approach to assessing environmental risk in this situation was apparent.

1.1 Purpose of this report

This report presents findings of a Rapid Environmental Impact Assessment (R-EIA) of the potential immediate impact associated with Nova Kakhovka Dam breach, Ukraine.

The Project Team were tasked by the FCDO with developing a R-EIA approach allowing an initial assessment of impacts across receiving ecosystems, combining openly available data and new hydrological and hydraulic modelling outputs with GIS and remote sensing products. The scope of the analysis was constrained to downstream of the dam breach, although consideration was also given to impacts on upstream geographies and features. The report focusses on the immediate impacts of the breach, although consideration is given also to longer term effects, for

example, including a description of flood recession, pollutant dispersal and persistence, and ecological recovery timescales.

The contents of this report are based on evidence available up to 24 June 2023. Owing to the need for swift delivery, this evidence was rapidly gathered and assessed during a two-week period, across the following Project Components.

- Component 1: To assess the flood hydrology, hydraulics and sediment transport following the dam breach
- Component 2: To conduct a GIS-based assessment to quantify impacts across key categories (e.g. extent of protected ecosystems, potential pollution sources flooded, proportions of land-use types impacted etc.)
- Component 3: To classify hazards informing the development and application of a plausible risk assessment approach across species, habitats and river basin scales
- Component 4: To identify potential issues of concern that warrant further assessment beyond the timescales of this project.

To avoid confusion, a consistent naming convention has been followed here in which the main river is the Dnipro River, and the dam immediately upstream of the Nova Kakhovka Dam is the Dnipro Dam, situated near Zaporizhzhia.

1.2 Approach to setting confidence levels of findings

The top-level findings of the report have been assigned one of four confidence ratings – High, Moderate, Low and Very Low – with respect to the estimated effects. Generally, where our results could be validated, and the validation data was considered accurate then a ‘High’ rating was applied. Where the accuracy of the validation data was questionable then the level was reduced to ‘Moderate’. Where no validation data were available the level is reduced to ‘Low’. Finally, where results are largely hypothetical and no validation data is available, then the confidence rating was reduced to ‘Very Low’.

The confidence rating on characterisation of the flood event and impact extent using hydraulic modelling validated by satellite imagery is considered to be ‘High’, in that the model outputs produced have been validated against satellite data. The hazard classification (i.e. identification of hazard types) is also considered to be of ‘High’ confidence and is validated against satellite data, where available.

However, on attempting to validate the scale of each hazard (e.g. the number and location of petrol stations that may represent pollution sources) using before and after satellite data, it became apparent that some potential hazards may already have been impacted by the ongoing conflict prior to the dam breach and so confidence in our estimates of risk associated with such hazards is 'Moderate'. For others, spatial data were not available without bilateral data sharing agreements which were impossible to establish within the delivery timescales and so confidence in the effects of such hazards is 'Low'.

It should be noted that we include an assumption in our risk assessment that hazards were plausible. We confirmed the habitats impacted and impact extent using modelled and satellite flood impact extent data, and so confidence in these results is 'High'. Detailed on-the-ground surveillance and access to controlled data sources will be required to increase confidence ratings on hazard effects on habitats for most pollutant types. Surveillance should consider impacts within and beyond the immediate flood impact zone quantified here.

2.0 Assessing the flood hydrology, hydraulics and sediment transport [Component 1]

2.1 Key findings

Hydraulic modelling

The hydraulic modelling of the dam-break has simulated three scenarios and associated flooding, to capture the uncertainty in the breach profile. Results of the two scenario simulations which are closest to available validation data indicate that:

- There is a good match to the corresponding satellite imagery for the maximum flood extents downstream of the dam.
- Peak water levels match well against anecdotal evidence in Kherson.
- Peak water depths were generally less than 2m in the urban areas.
- Maximum water speeds on the floodplain were generally less than 1 m/s.
- The peak of the event was attenuated across a period of about two days.

Impacts on seasonal flood regime

- The Nova Kakhovka Dam and reservoir do not appear to have been specifically designed for flood control.
- Some reduction in flood flows would normally have been expected, caused by attenuation within the reservoir owing to its size and shape. However, the analysis does not clearly show this.
- A review of flow hydrographs has been carried out for recent floods that occurred in 1970, 1979 and 1981. For the purposes of these conclusions, the 1970 flood is referred to as a major flood, the 1979 flood as a medium flood, and the 1981 flood as a small flood.
 - Data from the 1970 flood indicate that the Nova Kakhovka Dam and Reservoir would have minimal impact on major floods because of the way in which it has been designed and operated, as the primary purpose is for water supply.
 - Data from the 1979 and 1981 floods indicate that the Nova Kakhovka Dam and Reservoir would generally have a small impact on medium and small floods although this would depend on the state of the reservoir when the flood occurred.

- It is therefore expected that the flood regime of the Lower Dnipro River without the Nova Kakhovka Dam will not change significantly compared with the situation before the breach. Flood flows may be slightly higher during medium and small floods but evidence from 1970 indicates that there would be little change in the flood regime in a major flood.

Sediment assessment

The following sediment related impacts could be expected downstream of the dam as a result of the flood caused by the breach of the Nova Kakhovka Dam:

- Erosion at the toe of infrastructure such as intakes, bank protection, or flood embankments and bridge piers and abutments, due to development of general bed and bank erosion;
- Increased suspended material in the water column, leading to increased turbidity causing the blockage of light penetration, lowering of levels of oxygen in water, suffocation of aquatic life and an increase in water treatment costs;
- Increased risk of pollution due to the capacity of the sediments in the reservoir to carry nutrients and chemical contaminants. In addition, the higher sediment transport capacity reduces the transit time of sediments and therefore reduces the opportunities for decay of pollutants attached to sediment on route to depositional zones;
- Destruction of habitats of stream organisms;
- Changes in the navigation channels.

It is possible that some of these factors could develop further over time resulting in a larger impact, but information is not presently available to enable an assessment of this.

2.2 Background and approach

The Nova Kakhovka Dam is the downstream dam of the Dnipro River cascade system consisting of six dams built between 1932 and 1976 over a distance of 855 km (Obodovskyi, 2020, Khilchevskyi et al., 2022) (Table 2.1). The Kakhovka Reservoir is the largest in Ukraine in terms of volume ($18.18 \times 10^9 \text{ m}^3$) and has a length of 230 km. The width varies from 3 km to 7 km in the first 90 km upstream of the dam and widens in the following 110 km (reaching up to 20 km wide). In the last 20 km, downstream of the Dnipro Dam (at Zaporizhzhia), there is a large island, Khortytsia Island, 12 km long and 2 km wide with two side channels around 400 m and 800 m wide. Kostyuk (2021) reports that the northern part of the island is rocky and steep, while the southern part is slightly sloping, with high vegetation.

Table 2.1. Characteristics of reservoirs of the Dnipro River cascade system from upstream to downstream

Dam	Year to fill	Catchment area (10 ³ km ²)	Average runoff (10 ⁹ km ³ /yr)	Reservoir volume (10 ⁹ km ³)	Surface area (km ²)	Length* (km)	Average depth* (m)
Kyiv	1966	239	33.1	3.73	922	110	4
Kaniv	1976	336	43.9	2.5	582	123	3.9
Kremenchuk	1961	383	47.8	13.52	2,252	149	6
Kamianske	1964	424	52	2.46	567	114	4.3
Dnipro (Zaporizhzhia)	1932	463	52.2	3.32	410	129	8
Kakhovka	1956	482	52.2	18.18	2,155	230	8.5

Sources: Values extracted from Khilchevskiy et al (2022) except * from Zheleznyak et al (1992)

2.3 Hydraulic modelling of dam breach and validation with satellite data

Simulation of the breach flow

In order to understand the development of the flooding downstream, in terms of the time series of flood extents, depths and velocities, as well as the duration of flooding, a hydraulic modelling approach was used. The results were also used in the subsequent sediment and environmental impacts analyses. One model simulated the outflow hydrograph from the dam, which formed the upstream boundary condition for a second model, representing the flooded area downstream of the dam. A one-dimensional (1D) model was developed to simulate the outflow hydrograph from the dam following the breach. There was high uncertainty in estimating the flow hydrograph because the dimensions of the breach and the bathymetry of the reservoir were not known. The width of the breach was therefore estimated from high resolution satellite images (from the European Space Agency's SkySat) as shown in Figure 2.1.

Fig. 2.1. Estimation of the range of breach width, annotated with reasonable assumptions of the width. Source: SkySat

The following scenarios regarding breach width, invert level, and some roughness parameters, were evaluated:

- Breach 1 – Breach width of 200 m with the breach invert at 4 m AD (~13 m below the water level);
- Breach 2 – Breach width of 450 m with the breach invert at 4 m AD;
- Breach 3 – Breach width of 450 m with the breach invert at 8 m AD;
- Breach 4 – Breach width of 800 m with the breach invert at 4 m AD;
- Breach 5 – Breach width of 800 m with the breach invert at 8 m AD;
- Breach 6 – Breach width of 450 m with the breach invert at 4 m AD with lower roughness.

Since the dam is made of concrete rather than being an earth embankment, and the breach is understood to have been caused by an explosion rather than by erosion, it was assumed in the model that the breach developed over a very short period of time. The modelled water levels in the location at the centre of the reservoir (by distance from the dam) were compared to satellite-derived lake levels from HydroWEB (<https://hydroweb.theia-land.fr/?lang=en&basin=DNIEPR>) (see Figure 1.1) and in-situ measurements reported by the Emergency Response Coordination Centre (ERCC) DG ECHO Daily Map dated 12 June 2023 (<https://erccportal.jrc.ec.europa.eu/ECHO-Products/Maps#/maps/latest>).

Figure 2.2 shows that across the 144-hour (6-day) period following the breach, the drawdown of water levels represented by 'Breach 6' compared best with the in-situ data. The volume of water released in the first two to three days following the breach also compares well with that stated in a *Nature* article from the 9 June 2023 (Naddaf, 2023). Figure 2.3 shows the simulated outflow hydrographs from each of the breach scenarios.

Fig. 2.2. Modelled reservoir water levels compared to in-situ data and satellite observations

Fig. 2.3. Modelled reservoir outflow hydrographs

Flood modelling

The flows were run in a two-dimensional (2D) model of the river and floodplain downstream of the dam, so that the movement of the water across the floodplain could be represented. The model had approximately 3 million mesh elements using a variable flexible mesh sized between 400 m² and 900 m² (equivalent to a 20 m by 20 m to 30 m by 30 m grid) with an average element size of 600 m²; through using a variable mesh size, higher resolution could be achieved in areas of highest spatial variability. The ground levels in the model mesh elements were taken from the Copernicus GLO-30 Digital Elevation Model (DEM); no bathymetric data were available for the river channel itself, so the channel dimensions were assumed based upon its ability to pass high flows under normal conditions. The model uses spatially-varying roughness (via the use of the Manning's n parameter) which is based on WorldCover land cover data as follows:

- Tree cover: assigned Manning's n of 0.10;
- Herbaceous wetlands, shrub and grasslands: assigned Manning's n of 0.07;
- Urban areas: assigned Manning's n of 0.30;
- River channels and lakes: assigned Manning's n of 0.03.

The 2D hydrodynamic model was run for the flow scenarios Breach 2, Breach 3, Breach 4 and Breach 6. Scenario Breach 1 was rejected at this stage because the maximum flood extent was notably smaller than observations and it did not simulate the observed drawdown of reservoir water levels well. Scenario Breach 5 was similar to Breach 2, though it resulted in slightly less outflow and slower drawdown than observations, so Breach 5 was rejected. Scenarios Breach 2 and Breach 6 were identified as offering the best fit to observations, so these were taken forwards. As a sensitivity analysis, scenarios Breach 3 and Breach 4 were kept as the lower and higher sensitivity runs, respectively.

Model validation

The maximum flood extent was compared with the following satellite images in a validation procedure:

- ICEYE Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR): 2023-06-07 13:00 UTC;
- European Space Agency (ESA) Sentinel-1: 2023-06-09 15:36 UTC.

Figure 2.4. Receding water levels from the Nova Kakhovka Dam breach inundation as observed by satellite images¹. Sources: ESA WorldCover © ESA WorldCover project / Contains modified Copernicus Sentinel data (2021) processed by ESA WorldCover consortium (see also Zanaga et al., 2022); UNOSAT ICEYE¹; Copernicus Sentinel 1.

This analysis identified that the flood extents with the Breach 2, 4 and 6 scenarios compared well with the processed satellite images. The smaller breach dimensions (Breach 3 scenario) did not replicate the maximum flood extents.

A peak observed water level in Kherson of 5.6 m is given in the *Nature* article (dated 9 June 2023); the model results at a location in Kherson compare well from scenarios Breach 4 and Breach 6. Based on the comparison of reservoir water levels, the flood extent and flood level in Kherson, the simulation scenario Breach 6 best represents the peak flood. The F-test, commonly used to compare flood outlines (Horritt and Bates, 2001), applied between the maximum modelled flood extent with Breach 6 and the ICEYE satellite derived flood extent on the 7 June is 96%. The comparison of the total area of land flooded from the two sources is 99.9%.

¹ <https://data.humdata.org/dataset/satellite-flood-water-extent-between-the-nova-kakhovka-dam-wall-and-the-dniro-river-mouth>

The Breach 6 scenario model results (Figures 2.5 and 2.6) show:

- Peak flood depths in the urban areas were generally less than 2 m;
- Peak flow speeds on the floodplain were generally less than 1 m/s.

Figure 2.5. Maximum modelled water depths.

Figure 2.6. Maximum modelled flow speeds.

The model was used to simulate the main period of flood recession through to 26 June. In order to simulate this recession, it was important to ensure that the volumes of water being simulated represented the total volume released from the reservoir. Based upon the sediment analysis (detailed in Section 2.4), the likely volume of available storage had been reduced by around 23% from the original full volume, giving 12.9 km³ being released for the flooding; this was the value used in the simulation. The modelling of the overall event showed that the peak flow speeds occurred during the rising flood wave in the first day, and the maximum flood extent occurred between days 0 (6 June) and 3 (9 June). The modelling indicates that the high flows from the dam breach started receding around 4 days after the breach (10 June), with flows returning to normal river flows 6 days (12 June) after the breach (near the dam) to 8 days (14 June) after the breach (at Kherson).

2.4 High level sediment transport assessment

The objective of this assessment was the high-level identification of sediment transport-related impacts due to the failure of Nova Kakhovka Dam. This assessment only dealt with the sediment transported by the river and did not investigate any other type of debris which may have been carried by the inundation when the dam was breached. The analysis covered the periods before and after the breaching of the dam, and for the latter, it looked at the conditions within the reservoir, and those downstream of the dam.

The sediment transport patterns in the Dnipro River were modified by the dams constructed in the mid 20th century (Table 2.1). Any dam leads to a reduction of river flow velocities and water surface slopes, decreasing the capacity of the river to transport sediment and encouraging its deposition within the reservoir.

Before the breaching of the Nova Kakhovka Dam

The large surface area of the Kakhovka Reservoir implies large shallow areas which favour sediment deposition and growth of aquatic vegetation and blue-green algae (Schevchuk et al, 2005). Applying Brune's method to estimate the rate at which sediment accumulates in the reservoir (see Efthymiou et al, 2017 and Morris & Fan, 1998) with the values from Table 2.1, the estimated trapping efficiencies are of the order of 95% in the two largest reservoirs of the system, Kakhovka and Kremenchuk; 88% in Kyiv; and 75-80% at the three smallest reservoirs: Kaniv, Kamianske and Dnipro (Zaporizhzhia).

These results indicate that:

- 95% of the sediment inflow to the Kakhovka Reservoir will deposit there;
- The operation of the upstream dams influences how much sediment travels down the river into the reservoirs downstream. Accordingly, sediment inflow into the Kakhovka Reservoir is modified by the operation of the upstream dams.

Khilchevskiy et al. (2022) report that Kremenchuk reservoir is the main regulator of water flows in the system, with its seasonal and annual variations.

The following information about sediment loads in the Dnipro River was available:

- Milliman and Farnsworth (2011) report a total suspended sediment load of 2.3 Mt/year from the Dnipro River into the Black Sea;
- Obodovskiy et al (2020) report that suspended sediment concentrations decreased from 31.6 mg/l to 23.0 mg/l after the construction of the Kyiv dam giving an idea of the order of magnitude of suspended sediments in the river (the original reference was published in a Ukrainian journal and was not available for this study).

Evidence of the build-up of sediment was revealed after the breach. Figure 2.7 shows an image from the Sentinel 2 satellite taken on 18 June 2023, revealing accumulations of historic sediments within the reservoir.

As well as interrupting the continuity of sediment transport through the river system depriving downstream reaches of material, dams also change the flow patterns. For example, Obodovskiy et al., (2020) identified that the Kaniv reservoir, further upstream in the Dnipro River cascade system, reduced annual flows, increased low water levels in summer months and introduced large hourly fluctuations.

Since the Kakhovka Reservoir was filled nearly 70 years ago (in 1956) (Khilchevskiy et al., 2022), the riverbed morphology downstream of the dam had already adapted to the flow regime imposed by the operation of the dam and new ecosystems were created and stabilised. The floodplain corridor downstream of the Nova Kakhovka Dam is about 4km wide with a main channel between 400m to 800m wide, several larger secondary channels (less than 200 m wide) separated by vegetated islands and many smaller channels, especially in the delta area, at the river mouth (Figure 2.8).

Figure 2.7 Sediment deposits in the Kakhovka Reservoir upstream of the Nova Kakhovka Dam (left) and 60km upstream (right) revealed by lowering water levels following the breach. Source: Copernicus Sentinel 2.

Figure 2.8. Mouth of the Dnipro River, 80km downstream of the Nova Kakhovka Dam. Source: Google Earth

The Dnipro River from the Nova Kakhovka Dam down to the river mouth is part of the Nizhnyodniprovsky National Park, which has different conservation objectives including the preservation of wetland areas (Figure 2.9).

Figure 2.9. Zone map of the lower Dnieper National Park (with protected and regulated areas). Source: Nizhnyodniprovsky National Nature Park website²

A United Nations Economic Commission report (UNEC, 2011) establishes discharge at the river mouth of 1,670 m³/s. The same report establishes an average discharge for the period 1952-1984 of 1,484 m³/s, with maximum and minimum values of 8,080 and 362 m³/s respectively.

After the breaching of the Nova Kakhovka Dam

In the reservoir

The sudden drawdown of water levels in the reservoir due to dam failure would have increased the sediment transport capacity and therefore, erosion of sediment deposits in the vicinity of the dam with a tendency for the erosion to rapidly progress upstream.

Results from the breach hydraulic model (described in Section 2.3) were used to estimate the evolution of bed shear stresses in the reservoir at different times after dam failure. The bed shear stress is expressed as:

$$\tau = \rho g \frac{(vn)^2}{Rh^{1/3}}$$

Equation 2.1: Bed shear stress equation where: τ is the bed shear stress, ρ density of water (1000 kg/m³), g gravitational acceleration (9.81 m²/s), v flow velocity, n Manning coefficient and Rh is the hydraulic radius

² <http://nppn.org.ua/>

The Manning coefficient ' n ' is assumed to be 0.03 and the hydraulic radius is assumed to be equal to water depth which is a valid assumption in wide cross-sections such as those in the Kakhovka Reservoir.

Figure 2.10 shows the modelled shear stresses in the Kakhovka Reservoir at varying distances upstream of the Nova Kakhovka Dam, at various time instances after the breach.

It can be seen that the highest shear stresses are localised in the first 40 km upstream of the dam, with another peak around 80-90km and lower values upstream of 100km, excepting another lower peak at 120km – 130km. The figure also shows the decrease in shear stresses as time passes, from average values around 4-5 N/m² upstream of the dam on the 6 June to half of these values on the 11 June.

The potential for mobilisation of bed material depends on exceeding a critical bed shear stress for initiation of motion. For granular material (sand and coarser particles), the critical shear stress can be defined as:

$$\tau_{cr} = 0.056 (\rho_s - \rho)gD$$

Equation 2.2: Critical shear stress, where ρ_s is the particle density (typically around 2,650 kg/m³) and D is the sediment particle diameter.

Figure 2.10. Modelled shear stresses in the Kakhovka Reservoir at different time instances after the breach.

Figure 2.10 also shows the critical shear stress for a medium sand with a representative diameter equal to 0.5 mm. It can be concluded that flow conditions in the reservoir due to dam failure could mobilise sediment deposits of medium sand located in the first 100 km of the reservoir since the shear stresses exceed this threshold. Sediment movement further upstream, in the upstream half of the reservoir, is less likely to occur. It must be considered, however, that as flow concentrates in channels created within the reservoir, the transport capacity of those channels (and therefore, their potential for erosion) could be higher. Also note that these estimates do not take into account the fine sediment (silt and clay) that is likely to have deposited in the reservoir and compacted by consolidation over time.

Figure 2.11 shows a Sentinel 2 image from 15 June showing some exposed sediment deposits in the area upstream of the dam, which become more clearly visible, along with the main river channel, in a Sentinel 2 image from the 18 June after a further lowering of water levels.

*Figure 2.11. Reservoir area upstream of the dam on the 15 June (left) and 18 June (right).
Source: Copernicus Sentinel 2*

In the wider area of the reservoir (between 90 and 200 km upstream of the dam) the visible channel system is more complex, with several secondary channels (Figure 2.12). The results from Figure 2.9 show that coarse sediment is not likely to be widely mobilised in this area.

*Figure 2.12. Channel system in the wide area of the reservoir, 90 km upstream of the dam.
Source: Sentinel 2 image from 19 June 2023*

A main channel between 400m and 800m wide is identified from satellite images across the whole reservoir. Comparison of recent satellite images with old maps around the dam area, shows that when water levels lowered due to failure of the dam, the flows were conveyed by a channel following a similar path to that which had existed prior to construction of the dam (the pre-impoundment channel). This is shown in Figure 2.13.

Figure 2.13. Main channel (dotted red line) upstream and downstream of the dam (denoted by the yellow circle in the top image) on the 18 June 2023 (top) and from a 1940s map (bottom). Sources: top - Copernicus Sentinel 2; bottom - National Archives Catalog (DIAA, 1944) map used to position aerial flight overlays between April 1941 and 1944

This observation confirms that, in the 67 years since the Nova Kakhovka Dam was built, sediment deposition in the reservoir has not completely filled the pre-impoundment main river path, at least in the areas closer to the dam and, therefore, the main submerged channels are still the deepest parts in the reservoir. In general, sediment deposition in reservoirs, initially focuses at the deepest part of the cross-sections, developing an almost flat bottom bed (Morris and Fan, 1998). It is possible that the operation of the Nova Kakhovka Dam during its lifetime (information unknown at the time of this analysis) or a limited sediment inflow from upstream had allowed the main channel paths to be maintained.

Downstream of the reservoir

After the dam failure, the river downstream of the dam responds to the new conditions created by the increased discharges.

The model results of the breach scenario (from Section 2.3) show that water depths reduced from 14 m to 3 m and flow speeds reduced from 4.5 m/s to 1 m/s in the main channel of the river downstream of the dam to the river mouth (Figure 2.14). The first 20 km downstream of the dam experienced higher flow velocities and deeper water depths. Water depths in the main channel were of the order of 3-4 m deeper than in the floodplains.

Figure 2.14. Modelled water depths and flow speeds along the main channel downstream of the Nova Kakhovka Dam following the breach. Source: HR Wallingford InfoWorks ICM hydraulic model

A range of maximum water depths and flow speed values along the main channel were used to estimate bed shear stresses, using the equation presented in the previous section. The results range from 4 N/m² to 220 N/m², depending on the combination of flow speeds and water depths. These values correspond to the worst combination of water depths and flow speeds.

Using the equation for critical shear stress presented in the previous section, the diameter of the sediment that could be mobilised has been estimated. Based on the flow shear stresses obtained above, the maximum flow would be able to mobilise particles smaller than 6 mm (fine gravel) for all combinations of maximum depths and velocities. Larger sediment sizes, of the order of cobbles could also be mobilized under certain combinations of flow. It is expected that as flow recedes, the transport capacity will reduce and only smaller particles, sand and finer material, could be mobilised. These estimations do not take into account whether the material to be mobilised is available in the channel, nor whether the river bed is armoured or stabilised by a mix of sediment sizes. For example, if there were any rock outcrops in the channel bed, the flow would not be able to erode it.

In the short term (during the first days after the dam failure), several processes may have taken place simultaneously such as short-term scour, deposition of material and increased suspended sediment concentrations.

Short-term scour during the flood event causes a lowering of bed levels within the incised channel (if bed material is erodible). As identified above, there is an increase in the sediment transport capacity of the river and, therefore, scour will develop if there is an imbalance between the amounts of sediment in transport at the upstream and downstream ends of the reach.

Several regime equations reported in Kirby et al., (2015) were used to estimate the potential short-term scour. Due to the lack of information about the characteristics of river sediment, it was assumed that the coarser sediment in the river bed could be a fine to medium sand. Based on this assumption, river bed erosion is estimated to be of the order of 1 to 3 m. As water recedes back to the main channel, the risk of erosion decreases as shown by the reduction of flow speeds and water depths a few days after the failure (Figure 2.15). The results obtained with the regime equations using water depths and flow velocities one week after failure estimate less than 0.5 m of erosion on average.

Figure 2.15. Modelled water depths and flow speeds 0 km downstream of the Nova Kakhovka Dam after failure. Source: HR Wallingford ICM hydraulic model.

Satellite images after the dam failure show areas downstream of the dam where vegetation was removed that could correspond to erosion processes (to be confirmed with field data or further information) (Figure 2.16).

Figure 2.16. Comparison of channel position 11 km downstream of the dam before (left, 5 June) and after (right, 18 June) dam failure. Areas of likely erosion are marked with orange arrows. Source: Copernicus Sentinel 2.

Areas with potential increased erosion risk are the vicinity of the dam, where flow velocities were very high during the breach, the outer bank of bends (where velocities are higher than in the middle of the channel and secondary currents develop), and narrower reaches where flow accelerates (increasing its potential for erosion). In the short term and depending on the bank material and the presence of protection works there may also be a tendency for the flow to attack the banks and thereby widen the channels.

Besides erosion processes, deposition of material transported by the river could also happen in areas where flow velocity decreases, for example where the river widens. From available satellite images it was not possible to visually identify sediment deposits. However, it is expected that fine sediment may have deposited in the floodplains as water receded.

Due to the increased transport capacity of suspended sediment and ongoing erosion and sedimentation processes, it is also expected that water turbidity may increase in the short term. It is also likely that, in the longer term, if lots of fine sediment has been remobilised into the system then it will be available for subsequent remobilisation in other, lesser, events, and as a whole the system may be more turbid for a prolonged period than in pre-breach years.

In the longer term (months to years), a new equilibrium will develop based on water discharges and operation of the upstream Dnipro Dam. For example, it is expected that higher discharges will occur downstream as releases into irrigation systems with intakes in the Kakhovka Reservoir may not be operational for a long period of time. The higher sediment transport capacity due to increased discharges may lead to incision of the main channel bed and increased bank erosion potential. Therefore, the river will adjust its cross-sections and planform to the new conditions. It is also expected that more sediment is likely to reach the river mouth.

Conclusions of the sediment transport assessment

The presence of the Nova Kakhovka Dam caused a reduction of the Dnipro River flow velocities and water surface slopes thereby decreasing the capacity of the river to transport sediment and encouraging its deposition within the reservoir. Based upon a small amount of available data, it has been estimated that up to 23% of the total reservoir capacity may have been lost due to sedimentation since the dam was constructed in 1956. It is recommended that this estimation is verified against other sources of information, if available.

Since 1956, the Dnipro river bed morphology downstream of the dam (a reach approximately 80 km long) adapted to the flow regime imposed by the operation of the dam and new ecosystems were created and stabilised.

In the reservoir area, the lowering of water levels due to the dam failure has exposed pre-impoundment submerged channels which, once again, are conveying the flow downstream.

The lowering of water levels and increase of flow velocities in the reservoir due to the dam failure has increased the transport capacity of the flow and mobilised deposited sediments in the reservoir through the breach. Preliminary results show that granular deposits of medium sand from the downstream half of the reservoir could be eroded.

The river planform downstream of the dam and the position of the main and larger secondary channels does not change overall after the dam failure. Changes are noticeable in some wetland areas, with an increase of water surfaces due to flooding.

The increased flow discharge downstream of the dam has increased the sediment transport capacity in the river reach. It is estimated that the flow conditions generated after failure would have been able to mobilise at least fine gravel particles (smaller than 6 mm).

In the short-term (days after the failure) it is expected that scour developed in the main channel causing the lowering of bed levels. Based on several equations it is estimated that erosion could be of the order of 1m to 3m for fine to medium sand material. As water recedes back to the main channel, the risk of erosion decreases (no information was available to this study about sediment characteristics). Erosion could be higher at bends and narrow reaches of the river. The flow would also tend to attack the banks and thereby widen the channel. Besides erosion processes, deposition may also happen in areas where flow velocity decreases and in the floodplains as water recedes. All these processes increase suspended solids content in the water column and increase turbidity.

In the long-term (from months to years), a new equilibrium will develop based on the new water regime (depending on the operation of the upstream Dnipro Hydro Power Plant with the corresponding dam) and the river will adjust its cross-sections and planform to the new conditions.

2.5 High-level assessments of impacts on the seasonal flood regime

In terms of understanding the potential impacts of the loss of Nova Kakhovka Dam on the seasonal flood regime of the lower Dnipro River, it is important to understand its function, and its role in the cascade. While Kakhovka Reservoir was the largest by volume of the cascade, the Kremenchuk Reservoir is the main regulator of runoff. The Kakhovka Reservoir provides water supply to an extensive network of canals which provide irrigation and potable water to large areas in southern Ukraine.

The Kakhovka Reservoir is very long (230 km) and has a large area (of 2,155 km²) but a relatively shallow average depth of 8.5 m. The primary functions of the dam and reservoir are water supply and hydropower generation. It also forms part of the Dnipro River navigation scheme.

With regard to flood control, the dam does not appear to be specifically designed for this purpose. Dams that are specifically designed for flood control have a volume within the reservoir that is allocated for flood storage together with large control gates that regulate the downstream flow under flood conditions.

It is understood that the operation of the Kakhovka Reservoir aims to store water during the main flood season (April to June), which is then used for water supply. If the capacity of the reservoir is exceeded by a flood, the surplus water flows over the dam spillway and passes downstream. There would normally be some reduction in flood flow caused by attenuation within the reservoir, where the water level rises above the level of the spillway and provides temporary storage as the rate of the outflow is controlled by the spillway. It was noted from the HydroWeb data (Figure 1.1) that water levels in the Kakhovka Reservoir were very high compared to the historical record just prior to the breach.

The impact of the Nova Kakhovka Dam on flooding has been assessed using data from the following historic floods for which data were available: 1970, 1979 and 1981.

- Flood flow data have been obtained for these floods at the following stations:
- Kyiv (grey line on the figures);
- Dnipro Dam (brown line on the figures). This is at the upstream end of the Kakhovka Reservoir;
- Kherson (blue line on the figures). This is downstream of the Kakhovka Dam.

The 1970 flood

Figure 2.17 shows the 1970 flood where the peak flow at Kyiv occurred on 22 April and was about 18,400 m³/s. The peak flow at the Dnipro Dam was about 9,350 m³/s on 3 May, about half of the peak flow at Kyiv. This indicates the impact of the Dnipro River cascade on flood flows. The 1970 flood was a major flood which is understood to be of the same order of magnitude as the previous largest floods of the 20th century, which occurred in 1917 and 1931.

The peak flow at Kherson was about 9,440 m³/s on 6 May, almost identical to the flow at the Dnipro Dam. The hydrograph shape and flood volume were also very similar. The only part of the hydrograph where the flow was higher at the Dnipro Dam was in late March, where the flow at the Dnipro Dam was less than 5,000 m³/s. The volume of this storage is estimated from the hydrographs as about 1.2 km³, which is about 15% of the “useful storage of regulation” for the Kakhovka Reservoir (Table 2 in Khilchevskyi et al, 2022).

This indicates that a limited amount of storage was available in the Kakhovka Reservoir but the bulk of the flood passed downstream via the dam spillway.

It is therefore concluded that the Kakhovka Dam had minimal impact on major floods because of the way in which it has been designed and operated. Whilst there may have been scope for using the reservoir to attenuate floods, the primary purpose was for water supply.

Figure. 2.17. 1970 flood hydrographs.

Figure 2.17 also shows the Spring 1971 flood season, where flows from Dnipro Dam were below 5,000 m³/s and some attenuation of downstream flows was provided by the Kakhovka Reservoir. Three flow peaks occurred, of which the first two were attenuated (thus reducing downstream flows) but the third was not, indicating that the reservoir would have been full.

The 1979 flood

Data for the 1979 flood were available for the Dnipro Dam, at the upstream end of the Kakhovka Reservoir, and Kherson, downstream of the Nova Kakhovka Dam. The flood occurred during the flood season, from about 7 April to 16 May 1979 (Figure 2.18). There were two flood peaks. The first and largest had almost identical peak flows of just over 6,000 m³/s at the Dnipro Dam and Kherson. The second peak was about 5,800 m³/s at the Dnipro Dam and about 4,900 m³/s at Kherson, indicating that there was some attenuation during the second peak, which occurred about three weeks after the first peak.

This suggests that the reservoir was full when the first peak occurred but there was some storage volume available for the second peak. It is therefore concluded that the Kakhovka Reservoir could provide modest amounts of flood attenuation although this would depend on the state of the reservoir when the flood occurred.

Figure. 2.18. 1979 flood hydrographs.

The 1981 flood

Data for the 1981 flood were available for the Dnipro Dam, at the upstream end of the Nova Kakhovka Reservoir, and Kherson, downstream of the Kakhovka Dam.

The flood occurred during the flood season, from about 1 April to 22 May 1981 (Figure 2.19). There were two flood peaks. The first had a peak flow of just over 4,600 m³/s at the Dnipro Dam on 12 April and the second had a peak flow of about just over 4,200 m³/s at the Dnipro Dam on 3 May. The corresponding peak flows at Kherson were just over 5,000 m³/s on 12 April and about 4,000 m³/s on 12 May.

Whilst there are minor fluctuations in the flows from the Dnipro Dam, probably related to gate operation, the shape and size of the hydrographs are similar for both peaks. The first peak has a higher flow at Kherson, indicating that there is likely to have been an inflow contribution from the catchment downstream of the Dnipro Dam.

Figure. 2.19. 1981 flood hydrographs.

Throughout the flood hydrographs, there are occasional spikes in flow at the Dnipro Dam. These are of very short duration and may either be errors in data or (more likely) short duration releases from the dam. The corresponding flow volumes would be small and their impacts on water levels in the Kakhovka Reservoir would be minimal.

3.0 Identification of impact indicators and assessment of impacts on high conservation status ecosystems and biodiversity [Component 2]

3.1 Key findings

Land cover and flooded infrastructure analysis

- Using the maximum modelled extent, 62% of the land inundated by the downstream flood from the Nova Kakhovka Dam breach is classified as herbaceous wetland; 5% is classified as built-up land; cropland is under 2%. There are additional horticulture installations that may increase the estimates of damage to crops.
- At least one wastewater treatment works, multiple industrial areas, at least two recycling plants (sources of possible pollution); one police station and two hospitals (emergency first response facilities) are situated within the maximum downstream flood extent caused by the Kakhovka Dam breach. Some of these affected installations are situated on the north bank and others on the south bank. Others are situated close to the maximum flood extent and may also be impacted.

Irrigation analysis

- The entrances to the three irrigation canals on the south bank of the Kakhovka Reservoir are visibly above the water level and the canals are drying out (North Crimean Canal, Kakhovsky Canal and the canal near Balky).
- The entrance to the canal on the north bank (canal near Maryanske) is also above the water level and is visibly drying out.
- Area designated as crop land which is at high risk of loss of irrigation due to the breach of the Kakhovka Dam in the Oblasts of Crimea, Kherson, Zaporizhzhia and Dnipropetrovsk totals 28,629km²

- An analysis of the satellite observed Normalised Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), a widely-used metric for quantifying the health and density of vegetation, did not provide clear evidence that crop land in Crimea was affected between 2014 and 2022 when it was last restricted. From this analysis it is therefore not possible to provide an indication of the magnitude of the impact on agricultural land due to the irrigation loss.

Impacted species, habitats, and sources of potential pollution

- In total, over 529,000 ha of land and water designated as being of special conservation interest, and with one or more levels of environmental protection, is potentially affected. This includes 138,000 ha downstream of the dam within the pre-flood / flooded water extents, 186,000 ha in nearby coastal areas and 205,000 ha within the pre-flood reservoir.
- Within the area of impact, a total of 138 species are listed under Article 4 of the Birds Directive or Annex II of the Habitats Directive and were important in designating habitat under the Emerald Network. A total of 125 species are also listed in the 4 coastal Emerald Network sites at the mouth of the Dnipro.
- Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) occurrence records from the affected area include 142 species in the Ukrainian Red Books and 567 in the European Red List – with some featuring in both. Of those in the Ukrainian Red Book, 86 (~60%) are at vulnerable status or worse. In the European Red List this figure is 28 (~5%).
- Within the modelled maximum flood extent, the collated pollution source dataset, compiled from open data, identified 1,088 features in 8 potential pollution categories, with a total area of ~4,300 ha.

3.2 Background and approach

To assess modes of impact across the flood zone, including indicators of land-use, high conservation status ecosystem and biodiversity exposure, population exposure and infrastructure inundation, spatial datasets were collated and built into a metadatabase (detailed in Appendix 1) and accompanying GIS tool. An Indicator Framework was developed to group spatial data (23 data sets compiled) into 4 categories: societal (e.g. hospitals, schools etc.), industrial (e.g. factories, power stations etc.), infrastructure (roads and railways), and environmental (terrestrial, freshwater, and coastal ecosystems).

To assess impact to land of different types and key infrastructure, the maximum satellite observed extent of the flood downstream of the Kakhovka Dam breach was

overlaid with a land cover map and maps showing the locations of key infrastructure. Where appropriate, the maximum satellite observed extent was compared to the maximum extent from the hydraulic model previously described. An irrigation analysis observed the canals connected to the reservoir and assessed the amount of crop land at risk from loss of irrigation by considering its connection to this network of canals. A Normalised Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) explored changes from when the water supply from the reservoir to Crimea was last restricted in 2014.

Important terrestrial, freshwater and aquatic habitats were analysed for impact using a compiled set of protected areas, then an interpretation of species-level data was performed at two scales: firstly, using a global dataset from the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) to give an overall assessment of impact across the flood zone and secondly, using species lists used to define the Emerald Network habitats that intersected the same area. Finally, the pollution source categories outlined in Component 3 were used to classify attributes in data from a combination of public, crowd-sourced datasets and government publications. This produced a spatial dataset of polygons that could assess potential pollution sources in the flood zone in both area and number.

It is important to note the following when interpreting these outputs:

- Analysis of impact on infrastructure and pollutant sources relied partly on open, crowd-sourced data, which is unlikely to represent all features on the ground.
- The maximum flood extents from UNOSAT and the hydraulic model might miss some affected areas on the ground, or over-estimate impact in some areas.
- Datasets show the pre-war state of the urban, agricultural, and environmental areas, where impact could have already been felt.
- Analysing the impact of floodwaters will not assess the impact upon the wider environment utilising the reservoir, where irrigation and drinking water supply would affect large areas outside the immediate downstream flood zone.
- When working with species data from multiple sources, the taxon names need to be harmonised. Where issues arose when harmonised species were assessed with different levels of concern or population trend, the 'worst case' assessment and/or trend has been selected.
- It has not yet been possible to harmonise all the species on the European Red List and Red Book Data of Ukraine to species within GBIF. The numbers in Table A5.1 are therefore likely to be a conservative assessment of the number of protected species in the areas of interest.

3.3 Land cover and flooded infrastructure analysis

Figure 3.1 shows land cover types taken from the ESA WorldCover land use dataset (<https://esa-worldcover.org/en/data-access>) overlaid with the maximum modelled flood water extent from the Nova Kakhovka Dam breach. The maximum extent observed by satellites is given by the ICEYE satellite image from 7 June 2023 and is very similar to the modelled extent.

Figure 3.1. Land cover types overlaid with the modelled downstream maximum flood water extent from the breach of the Nova Kakhovka Dam. Sources: HR Wallingford ICM hydraulic model and © ESA WorldCover project / Contains modified Copernicus Sentinel data (2021) processed by ESA WorldCover consortium (see also Zanaga et al., 2022)

Table 3.1 shows the land cover types (not including permanent areas of water), taken from the ESA WorldCover land use dataset, inundated by the breach of the Nova Kakhovka Dam, giving number of hectares (ha) and percentage of total, for both the maximum modelled extent (Figure 2.5) and the maximum satellite observed extent (Figure 2.4). The agreement between them is very strong and so there is a high degree of certainty in the results. Any uncertainty is more likely to come from inaccuracies in the land cover classifications.

Both sources agree that just over 62% of the inundated land is classified as herbaceous wetland and that 5% is built-up land. The amount of cropland inundated is relatively small at under 2% of the total (871 ha or 1.6% according to the model and 675 ha or 1.3% according to the satellite). Appendix 2 provides a detailed analysis of different land cover / habitat datasets for both flood extents.

Further analysis of satellite images reveals a gradual transition from cropland to built-up land, characterised by horticulture installations such as greenhouses or polytunnels as seen in the example in Figure 3.2. This may lead to uncertainty in the value of agriculture / horticulture lost in the flood.

Table 3.1 Land cover types flooded by the inundation from the Nova Kakhovka Dam represented by the maximum modelled and observed extents, not including areas of permanent water

Land cover type	Maximum modelled extent (07/06/2023-09/06/2023)		Maximum satellite observed extent (ICEYE 07/06/2023 12:18-13:01 UTC)	
	Affected area (ha)	Affected area (%)	Affected area (ha)	Affected area (%)
Tree cover	8333	15.7%	8043	15.5%
Grassland	8186	15.4%	8293	16.0%
Cropland	871	1.6%	675	1.3%
Built-up	2666	5.0%	2576	5.0%
Bare / sparse vegetation	68	0.1%	69	0.1%
Herbaceous wetland	32973	62.1%	32301	62.2%
Total	53097	100.0%	51958	100.0%

Figure 3.2. Horticulture installations downstream of the Nova Kakhovka Dam. Sources: Google Earth, image copyright 2023 Maxar Technologies and UNOSAT ICEYE³

Two similar figures show the key infrastructure lying downstream of the Nova Kakhovka Dam which have been flooded or are situated close to the maximum flood extent. At the time of writing the north bank is held by Ukraine and the south bank by Russia. Figure 3.3 shows the maximum observed downstream flood extent (taken from the ICEYE satellite image) overlaid with waste water treatment works, industrial areas and recycling plants. Those which lie within the maximum flood extent are denoted with red symbols. It can be seen that at least one waste water treatment works, multiple industrial areas and at least two recycling plants lie within this area. Figure 3.4 shows the maximum observed downstream flood extent (again taken from the ICEYE satellite image) overlaid with emergency services premises. Again, those which lie within the maximum flood extent are denoted with red symbols. One police station and two hospitals lie within this area.

³ <https://data.humdata.org/dataset/satellite-flood-water-extent-between-the-nova-kakhovka-dam-wall-and-the-dnipro-river-mouth>

Figure 3.3. Waste water treatment works, industrial areas and recycling plants within and near the maximum observed flood extent from the Nova Kakhovka Dam breach.

Sources: Google Earth, UNOSAT ICEYE (see previous footnote), Ordnance Survey Open Street Map, HydroWaste.

Figure 3.4: Emergency services premises within and near the maximum observed flood extent from the Nova Kakhovka Dam breach. Sources: Google Earth, UNOSAT ICEYE (see previous footnote), Ordnance Survey Open Street Map.

3.4 Irrigation analysis

Images from the European Space Agency (ESA) Sentinel 2 satellite show that, following the breach of the Nova Kakhovka Dam on 6 June 2023, by the 18 June the Kakhovka Reservoir had drained to the point where the original river channels could clearly be seen. Images on the 20 and 23 June show that the reservoir continued to drain. This is shown in Figure 3.5.

Lake Kakhovka pre and post dam breach

0 2.5 5 km

Coordinate System:
ETRS89-extended / LAEA Europe

Basemap: © OpenStreetMap contributors

hrwallingford
Produced by HR Wallingford Ltd. © 2023

Figure 3.5. Satellite images of the Kakhovka Reservoir before and after the breach of the Nova Kakhovka Dam. Source: Copernicus Sentinel 2

Irrigation canals were fed from the Kakhovka Reservoir serving large agricultural areas, particularly to the south of the reservoir and into Crimea. Figure 3.6 shows the waterways around the Kakhovka Reservoir as identified by Ordnance Survey Open Street Maps (OSM) with the three irrigation canals on the south side of the reservoir marked in orange and one on the north side. The Kherson region is marked in grey.

Figure 3.6. Rivers and canals in the vicinity of the Kakhovka Reservoir, the main irrigation canals are marked in orange, on the south bank from left to right: North Crimea Canal, Kakhovsky Canal, canal near Balky; on the north bank the canal near Maryanske.

The lowering of water levels has cut off these canals from the water supply in the reservoir. Figures 3.7, 3.8, and 3.9 show the entrances of the North Crimean Canal, the Kakhovsky Canal and the canal near Balky into the Kakhovka Reservoir before and after the dam breach. They clearly show the water level dropping below the level of the canal entrances. This was also reported by the BBC on the 22 June (Rivault, et al., 2023).

Figure 3.7. North Crimean Canal entrance before and after the breach of the Nova Kakhovka Dam. Source: Copernicus Sentinel 2

Figure 3.8. Kakhovsky Canal entrance before and after the breach of the Nova Kakhovka Dam. Source: Copernicus Sentinel 2

Figure 3.9. Entrance to the canal near Balky before and after the breach of the Nova Kakhovka Dam. Source: Copernicus Sentinel 2

There is a fourth canal on the north bank of the Kakhovka Reservoir near Maryanske. Figure 3.10 shows that the water level in the reservoir is now below the entrance and by the 23 June this canal was also drying up. An analysis of the topography indicates that this canal provides a link to a smaller lake, at an elevation of around 100m above the level of the reservoir, to the North-West, which is also understood to be for irrigation water supply.

Figure 3.10. Entrance to the canal near Maryanske before and after the breach of the Nova Kakhovka Dam. Source: Copernicus Sentinel 2

An analysis of the areas of crop land which are most dependent on the irrigation from these canals has been conducted, based on their connection to the canals as opposed to natural rivers as identified by the hydrographic baseline from the HydroSHED v10 dataset level 8 basins⁴. In the absence of detailed information on the irrigation system, it has been assumed that areas with natural rivers are less dependent on irrigation, although crop land within the river catchments and not fed by the canals may still be at risk. Table 3.2 shows the results of this analysis for the affected Oblasts (Provinces / Regions) of Crimea, Dnipropetrovsk, Kherson and Zaporizhzhia.

⁴ <https://www.hydrosheds.org/products/hydrosheds>

Figure 3.11 Crop land evaluated as being at high risk due to the loss of the irrigation canals connected to the Kakhovka Reservoir. Source: HR Wallingford and HydroSHEDS v10⁵. © ESA WorldCover project / Contains modified Copernicus Sentinel data (2021) processed by ESA WorldCover consortium

Table 3.2. Crop land at high risk of loss of irrigation due to the breach of the Kakhovka Dam

Oblast (Province / Region)	Area of crop land at high risk (km ²)
Crimea	10764
Kherson	10458
Zaporizhzhia	5085
Dnipropetrovsk	2322
Total:	28629

When Russia annexed Crimea in 2014, Ukraine restricted the water supply to occupied Crimea (see, for example, BBC, 2014). This action would have had a similar effect on the irrigation in Crimea to the Nova Kakhovka Dam breach. The area between the Kakhovka Reservoir and the Crimea in Kherson and Zaporizhzhia

⁵ <https://www.hydrosheds.org/products/hydrosheds>

retained its water supply from the North Crimea Canal, the Kakhovsky Canal and the canal near Balyk. During this period, it would therefore be expected to see a reduction in agricultural production in Crimea owing to the loss of irrigation, but not in the areas of Kherson and Zaporizhzhia between the Kakhovka Reservoir and Crimea.

The Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) is a widely-used metric for quantifying the health and density of vegetation using data from sensors mounted on satellites⁶. NDVI has a value between 1 and -1, where 1 indicates dense, healthy vegetation, 0 indicates nothing growing and values below 0 indicate a lack of dry land. NASA's VNP13A3 v001 product was used to provide monthly vegetation NDVI values at a resolution of 1km derived from Visible Infrared Imaging Radiometer Suite (VIIRS) data from January 2012 to May 2023. ESA WorldCover data was down-sampled from its native 10m resolution to 1km to match the VNP13A3 v001 data, indicating areas of crop land. The average NDVI for these areas was calculated for each Oblast, for each month.

Figure 3.12 shows the monthly NDVI values of land designated as crop land in Crimea from Jan 2012 through to May 2023. There is no pattern of reduction in NDVI values in the years following 2014 when the water supply was restricted. The Kherson region is marked in grey in Figure 3.6, and orange in Figure 3.11 and constitutes the larger part of the agricultural region between the Kakhovka Reservoir and Crimea. Figure 3.13 shows the NDVI values for crop land in Kherson over the same time period. The NDVI pattern appears similar to that of Crimea. The remainder of the agricultural land south of the Kakhovka Reservoir is in Zaporizhzhia. Figure 3.14 shows the NDVI values there for the same time period which, again, show a pattern similar to that of Crimea.

⁶ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Normalized_difference_vegetation_index

Figure 3.12 NDVI of areas designated as crops from Jan 2012 – May 2023 in Crimea.
 Source: © ESA WorldCover project / Contains modified Copernicus Sentinel data (2021)
 processed by ESA WorldCover consortium and NASA VNP13A3 v001

Figure 3.13 NDVI of areas designated as crops from Jan 2012 – May 2023 in Kherson.
 Source: © ESA WorldCover project / Contains modified Copernicus Sentinel data (2021)
 processed by ESA WorldCover consortium, and NASA VNP13A3 v001

Figure 3.14 NDVI of areas designated as crops from Jan 2012 – May 2023 in Zaporizhzhya. Source: © ESA WorldCover project / Contains modified Copernicus Sentinel data (2021) processed by ESA WorldCover consortium, and NASA VNP13A3 v001

This analysis of NDVI does not reveal any discernible difference in vegetation in Crimea in the years after it was last restricted from irrigation from the Kakhovka Reservoir in 2014. Indeed, the NDVI values are similar to those in neighbouring Kherson and Zaporizhzhya which were not restricted from the irrigation. This is due to the limitations of the NDVI analysis. NDVI by itself provides information about the greenness of landcover but it does not provide information about irrigation sources, types of crops or amount of precipitation. It is also not clear if the North Crimean Canal was completely shut between 2014 and 2022 or if some water was provided. From this analysis alone it is therefore not possible to provide a clear indication of the magnitude of the expected impact on agriculture due to the loss of irrigation originating from the Kakhovka Reservoir.

3.5 Impacted species

Analysis of potentially affected species was performed on a combined area of pre-flood water extent (using Sentinel-2 images acquired on 3 and 5 June 2023) and predicted flood extent (using Sentinel-3, Sentinel-2 and ICEYE images acquired on 6, 7 and 9 June 2023), both from UNOSAT (2023a). This includes the pre-flood reservoir and some of the Dniprovskia Gulf and is shown in Figure 3.15.

Figure 3.15. Map showing the effect of floodwaters on the environment. Potentially affected areas derived from UNOSAT pre-flood / flooded water extents and digitised pre-flood reservoir boundary. Emerald Network and Ramsar site boundaries from The World Database on Protected Areas.

3.5.1 Global dataset

A dataset from the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) was compiled using occurrence record data from 1960 onwards, sourced on 16 June 2023 ([GBIF Occurrence Download](#)). There are ~11,400 species/subspecies in the European Red List; we were able to search for ~11,370 of these within the GBIF records data (after standardisation of taxonomy, this relates to ~11,220 different taxon within the GBIF data). There are ~1,540 species/subspecies in the Ukrainian Red Books (plant and animal). From this, we were able to search for ~1,470 within the GBIF records data (after standardisation of taxonomy, this relates to ~1,455 different taxon within the GBIF data).

Allowing for some coordinate uncertainty of GBIF records, it is likely that only small differences would result from the choice of satellite data used to determine the flood extent. We identified ~3,900 records that intersect with the pre-flood water extents and predicted flood extent, relating to ~600 species/subspecies. 142 of these relate to species/subspecies in the Ukrainian Red Books and 567 (~5% of all species) in

the European Red List (some are in both). Of those in the Ukrainian Red Book, 86 (~60%) are at vulnerable status or worse. In the European Red List this figure is 28 (~5%). For comparison, the whole of Ukraine has 147 globally threatened species (vulnerable status or worse), whereas the United Kingdom has 200 (IUCN, 2023). These 28 species include freshwater or semi-aquatic species at direct risk of mortality, habitat degradation or disruption of breeding, as well as species of terrestrial habitats which will be affected in inundated areas, and species that use freshwater habitats as part of their migratory routes. Endangered terrestrial species include the Great Bustard (*Otis tarda*), European roller (*Coracias garrulus*), Dalmatian pelican (*Pelecanus crispus*) and Speckled ground squirrel (*Spermophilus suslicus*). Endangered freshwater and semi-aquatic species include the European mink (*Mustela lutreola*) and Pygmy cormorant (*Microcarbo pygmaeus*). There are also endangered populations that represent significant parts of that species' global range, such as the Black Sea salmon (*Salmo labrax*), Donets ruffe (*Gymnocephalus acerina*) and Russian desman (*Desmana moschata*). Although potential impact on threatened species at a European scale appears less severe in terms of number of threatened species affected, the Black Sea coast of Ukraine is home to important global populations of several species, even though they are currently assessed at least concern, such as the Mediterranean Gull *Larus melanocephalus* (Bird Life International, 2023). A detailed breakdown of the results from the GBIF analysis is shown in Appendix 3.

3.5.2 Habitat-level dataset

An initial analysis was undertaken of protected areas within the combined satellite-detected waters extent from UNOSAT combined with the pre-dam breach reservoir extent and the maximum predicted extent from the hydraulic model. Protected areas were taken from the UNEP-WCMC / IUCN World Database on Protected Areas (WDPA, 2023). Table 3.3 shows how these two extents differ in terms of the protected areas represented. For analysing global taxonomic data (at 1km resolution), a single extent (UNOSAT extent and the reservoir) was used. For analysing protected areas, analysis was run on both extents.

Table 3.3. All protected areas (PA) and their area statistics within the UNOSAT flood extent and the maximum modelled food extent

PA Name	PA Type	Total Area of PA (ha)	UNOSAT - area in flood extent (ha)	UNOSAT - % of PA affected	HRW - area in flood extent (ha)	HRW - % of PA affected
Dniprovsko-Buzkyi Lyman	Emerald Network	71521	70120	98.0%	15281	21.4%
Lower Dnipro	Emerald Network	52631	51090	97.1%	50443	95.8%
Dnipro River Delta	Ramsar Site, Wetland of International Importance	31020	30030	96.8%	29500	95.1%
Biloberezhzhia Sviatoslava	Emerald Network	35340	12460	35.3%	0	0.0%
Lower Inhulets river valley	Emerald Network	13651	2730	20.0%	1918	14.1%
Oleshkivski Pisky	Emerald Network	46500	960	2.1%	0	0.0%
Black Sea Biosphere Reserve	Emerald Network	116250	100	0.1%	0	0.0%
Chernomorskiy	UNESCO-MAB Biosphere Reserve	73540	60	0.1%	0	0.0%
Chernomorskiy	Biosphere Zapovednik	73540	60	0.1%	0	0.0%
Kinburnska Kosa	Emerald Network	46759	5	0.0%	369	0.8%
Loess outcrops of the Dnipro estuary	Emerald Network	592	0	0.0%	3	0.5%

The majority of the reservoir itself and the downstream affected area, all the way to where the Dnirovka Gulf meets the Black Sea, are under environmental protection (forming the Dnipro River Eco-Corridor), so several Ramsar and Emerald Network Sites are affected in their entirety (Figure 3.13). Other protected areas show only some of their area affected, though those on the Black Sea coast beyond the Dnirovka Gulf may be affected even where overlap is small. In total, over 529,000 ha of land and water designated as being of special conservation interest, and with one or more levels of environmental protection, is potentially affected. This is ~90% of the total predicted area of flood impact and includes 138,000 ha downstream of the dam within the UNOSAT pre-flood / flooded water extents, 205,000 ha within the

reservoir itself and 186,000 ha in the Black Sea biosphere and associated coastal area. These figures match well with a recent report by the Ukrainian Nature Conservation Group, who estimated the total impacted area as 500,000 ha (UNCG, 2023).

Table 3.4 shows the results of the species analysis on Emerald Network sites and their associated European Red List categorisation. Of the 138 species identified, 12 (~9%) are threatened at a European level (vulnerable status or worse).

Table 3.4. Article 4 / Annex II species, shown by European Red List category, for the affected Emerald Network sites

Taxonomic group / status	Species on Article 4 Bird directive/Annex II of Habitats directive by European Red List category*						Total
	LC	NT	VU	EN	CR	DD	
Amphibians	2	1					3
Birds	80	5	3	3	1	2	94
Fish	10		1				11
Invertebrates	2	3	1			5	11
Mammals	3	2	1	1		1	8
Plants	2					6	8
Reptiles		1	1			1	3
	Total						138

*LC = Least Concern, NT = Near Threatened, VU = Vulnerable, EN = Endangered, CR = Critically Endangered, DD = Data Deficient / Status Unknown

An extended freshwater plume will have occurred at the mouth of the Dnipro, affecting coastal habitats. There are four Emerald marine and Coastal reserves located in this area (Figure 3.16) - the Black Sea Biosphere Reserve (116 species listed with 1 species critically endangered), Biloberezhzhia Sviatoslava National Nature Park (87 species listed), Dniprovsko-Buzkyi Lyman (75 species listed with 1 species critically endangered) and Kinburnska Kosa (66 species listed). In total, there are 125 unique species in these 4 reserves and 12 (~10%) are threatened at a European level (vulnerable status or worse). Table 3.5 shows the European Red List species and their category, for the four coastal Emerald Network sites.

Figure 3.16. Map showing the four Emerald Network sites used in the coastal species analysis. The maximum modelled flood extent is shown in yellow.

Table 3.5. Article 4 / Annex II species, shown by European Red List category, for the four coastal Emerald Network sites.

Taxonomic group / status	Species on Article 4 Bird directive/Annex II of Habitats directive by European Red List category*						Total
	LC	NT	VU	EN	CR	DD	
Amphibians	2						2
Birds	80	5	3	3	1		92
Fish	10		1				11
Invertebrates	1	2	1			3	7
Mammals	3	2	1	1		1	8
Plants						2	2
Reptiles		1	1			1	3
						Total	125

*LC = Least Concern, NT = Near Threatened, VU = Vulnerable, EN = Endangered, CR = Critically Endangered, DD = Data Deficient / Status Unknown

The Black Sea bottlenose dolphin (*Tursiops truncatus ponticus*) is a subspecies of the common bottlenose dolphin and recorded within the Black Sea Biosphere reserve. Harbour porpoise are also recorded in the Reserve and Biloberezhzhia Sviatoslava National Nature Park. The Pontic shad (*Alosa immaculata*), also referred to as the Black Sea shad, is a species of fish, native to the Black Sea and Sea of Azov and recorded in Dniprovsko-Buzkyi Lyman and Black Sea Biosphere Reserve. Otters (*Lutra lutra*), beaver (*Castor fiber*), the Stepp polecat (*Mustela eversmanii*) are all recorded within the coastal reserves. The critically endangered slender-billed curlew (*Numenius tenuirostris*) has been recorded in the region, with numbers globally thought to be less than 50 individuals. The Dnipro delta is important as a staging post for migratory and breeding birds including the near threatened, red-breasted goose (*Branta ruficollis*).

3.6 Potential sources of chemical pollution

The collated pollution source dataset was restricted to the modelled flood zone and contains a total of 1087 polygon features representing an area of ~4300 ha. Feature counts and areas by pollution source type are detailed in Table 3.6. Figure 3.17 shows the spatial distribution of these pollution source types across the flood zone.

Table 3.6. Count and area of potential pollutant source features within the modelled maximum extent of the flood zone

Pollutant category	Feature count	Total area (ha)
farming	176	1130.3
fuel	8	5.3
industrial	199	624.5
landfill	4	22.2
mining	5	23.6
settlement	693	2464.0
shipping	1	0.005
wastewater	2	1.3

Figure 3.17. Collated pollution source dataset showing likely locations of pollutant source categories.

The accompanying GIS tool (Figure 3.18) provides an intuitive system to analyse these features and compare them to mapping and aerial imagery, as well as providing a mechanism for the risk assessment in Component 3. Comparison to satellite-derived likely impact areas in Kherson (Figure 3.19) shows a similar pattern of impact, with many of the affected areas containing pollution sources - differences here reflect the open, spatial datasets available versus satellite detection, and variation in the modelled and actual flood zones. 19% of Kherson City (12 km²) has been affected by floodwaters with 4,302 individual structures and 76 harbours affected (UNOSAT, 2023b), with flood-impacted features identified from aerial imagery. Identification in this way will be a valuable tool for furthering this work, with key infrastructure (such as harbours) currently difficult to obtain.

Figure 3.18. The GIS tool showing a detailed view of possible pollution sources and modelled flood extent (orange line). Layers can be turned on and off and examined against different background mapping to enable quality assurance.

Figure 3.19. Comparison of potential pollution sources affected by flood waters (left) in Kherson City against satellite-identified affected areas from UNOSAT (right).

4.0 Development and application of a risk-based assessment approach including hazard classification and preliminary risk assessment [Component 3]

4.1 Key findings

- We identify 21 habitats affected by 15 biological, chemical, environmental, meteorological and hydrological, and geohazards that have the potential to impact biodiversity and ecosystems, because of the Nova Kakhovka Dam breach.
- These hazards act through the mobilisation and transport of nutrients and pollutants, physical transformation of river network, reservoir water level reduction, and catastrophic downstream flooding.
- Based upon expert assessment of the available evidence, the risks posed to biodiversity and ecosystems vary along the upstream-downstream continuum of the Dnipro River system. Upstream, for the reservoir and associated Protected Areas, the impacts of rapid water level reduction (stranding and loss of organisms, habitat drying) are likely to be significant. Downstream of the reservoir, organism loss, inundation, and the erosion and deposition of contaminated sediments are likely to have significant impacts.
- There is a possibility of significant and ongoing impacts associated with the exposure of organisms to mobilised pollutants. These impacts may result from the movement of existing polluted sediments, and the release of new pollution due to impacts on infrastructure. In the immediate aftermath, areas around and downstream of the point of release are likely to experience the highest chemical concentrations and potential impacts.

4.2 Background and approach

We developed narrative descriptions of the most likely environmental hazards arising from the Nova Kakhovka Dam breach, based upon expert opinion and assessment of readily available information on the ecology of the region, available imagery and datasets, scientific reports that could be accessed, and information on the developing situation within the media. These descriptions provide the reasoning

behind each of the hazards selected for inclusion in this R-EIA. We note that although the Zaporizhzhia Nuclear Power Plant was not reported to be a contemporary pollution source, we have also included a narrative risk assessment for it given the heightened risk associated with cooling water access. In addition, we also created a section which explores the many other potential pollution sources that might impact upon the Protected Areas.

Following this, we aligned our identified hazards with the framework proposed by the UN Office for Disaster Risk Reduction (UNDRR & ISC, 2020). This framework classifies hazards using a hierarchic structure, according to a series of “clusters” within a series of “types”. We recognise that any given hazard (e.g. habitat scouring, sediment deposition) will have different impacts on different ecosystems. Using the expertise within the project team, we explored the likely impacts of each identified hazard on all of the Protected Areas for which we had information (see Component 2). Thus, we considered the likely severity of impact of each hazard, considering reported information and current initially available knowledge of the location of the flood extent and flow dynamics (from Component 1), and key infrastructure within the affected regions. Following this approach, Risks were classified as either:

- Low: hazard is unlikely to have a severe impact on the focal ecosystem
- Medium: moderate likelihood of a severe impact on the focal ecosystem
- High: hazard is very likely to have a severe impact on the focal ecosystem
- Not relevant: the hazard in question does not apply to the focal ecosystem

Levels of risk assigned by any single delivery team member were checked by at least one other team member with relevant background knowledge, to reach a consensus assessment.

4.3 Hazard categorisation

The delivery team identified and developed narrative descriptions for 15 specific environmental hazards (Appendix 1). We assigned these specific hazards to 7 hazard clusters, within 5 overarching UN hazard types. These hazards are:

4.3.1 UN hazard type & hazard cluster: biological – aquaculture

Impacts on habitats and biodiversity in Kakhovka Reservoir:

Growth of “algal” blooms in reservoir. Drastic reductions in reservoir depth can be associated with higher water temperatures and better illumination throughout the remaining, shallower water column. These conditions may favour the growth of potentially toxic phytoplankton blooms (including cyanobacteria), with implications for

water quality. This hazard would be relevant when the water was lost from the reservoir but will also be important if/when it is refilled in the future.

4.3.2 UN hazard type and hazard cluster: chemical – toxic substances, bioaccumulative substances & radionuclides

The pollution risks resulting from the dam breach will be a combination of both the mobilization of existing pollutants in the river system (e.g. contaminated sediment from the Kakhovka Reservoir) and the release of chemicals from compromised infrastructure (see section 4.3.8 for more detail behind these pollution sources). The impacts will be governed by a combination of the scale of the release, the hazards of the substances and their persistence in the receiving environment. In the initial phase, greatest impacts will be in the local areas around sites of release of larger volumes of high hazard chemicals, such as oil and fuel facilities (main pollutants petroleum hydrocarbons, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons), industrial sites (main pollutants industrial chemicals, solvents, heavy metals) and any stored agrochemicals (main pollutants pesticides and fertilisers). In these cases, effects are likely to be directly on exposed species living in the vicinity or immediately downstream of the release points. In the long-term, released chemicals will be transported away from their original sites of release. During this time, some of the more labile substances (e.g. some solvent, low persistence hydrocarbons and pesticides) will degrade. Those chemical with high persistence (e.g. metals, PAHs, persistent organic pollutants, some industrial chemicals) will remain in the systems. The accumulation of these chemicals, and hence the greatest potential for impacts to occur are likely to be in areas where pollutants are deposited through sedimentation. In those cases, persistent pollutants, such as toxic metals and persistent organic pollutants (POPs) will represent the greatest risk. In these cases, effects may be directly for exposed species. However, because some of these chemicals accumulate in the food web, impacts for species not directly exposed, can also be affected by chemical transfer through contaminated food.

4.3.3 UN hazard type and hazard cluster: environmental – environmental degradation

Impacts on habitats and biodiversity in Kakhovka Reservoir:

Stranding of aquatic organisms. The Kakhovka Reservoir and lower Dnipro Basin have a diverse fish fauna. The reservoir is reported to have hosted 43 freshwater fish species, 20 of which have commercial importance (Ukrainian Nature Conservation Group, UNCG, 2023), while 60-65 species are noted in the lower river basin more broadly (EU River Basin Management Plan, 2025-2030). The rapid loss of reservoir

volume has stranded large numbers of fish and has done so during the spawning period of many species, with negative implications for both the current fish stocks and future recruitment of fish to these stocks.

Direct loss of organisms. In addition to the stranding of large numbers of aquatic organisms, the high energy water flows are very likely to have swept organisms downstream, and towards the higher-salinity environment of the Black Sea (UNCG, 2023), resulting in significant mortality.

Emergence of aquatic habitats. The rapid loss of water level immediately following the dam breach will have exposed inshore sediments to the air, allowing “littoral” and “benthic” habitats to dry out. This poses risks to the invertebrate species (insects, crustaceans, molluscs) that inhabit the reservoir bed, and that are themselves important food resources for other species, including fish, birds, and amphibians. Similarly, aquatic plant species will desiccate under such conditions. This could increase the risk of non-native invasive species colonising in such areas. The freshwater bodies of the Dnipro basin are inhabited by approximately 100 bird species, for which recent events will represent a major disturbance to breeding and feeding areas. According to a UNCG assessment, the changing water levels threaten several rare habitat types recognised under the Bern Convention (Council of Europe, Convention on the Conservation of European Wildlife and Natural Habitats, 1982), as well as nationally (National Nature and Regional Landscape Parks) and internationally (Emerald Network sites) important protected areas. As a specific example of the biodiversity importance of such wetlands, the Sim Maiakiv Floodplain Ramsar site is recorded to host 137 birds, 24 mammals, 47 fish, 690 insects, and 326 plant species.

Impacts on habitats and biodiversity in the Lower Dnipro River:

Direct loss of aquatic organisms. Aquatic plants, invertebrates, and fish can be physically swept away by flood waters during catastrophic events, resulting in reductions in both the abundance and biodiversity of these organisms. In the Dnipro River tens of fish species, including migratory species, semi-aquatic mammals (otters, mink, beaver), amphibians (approximately 10 species), and invertebrates such as crayfish will have been exposed to this risk. Recolonization of organisms after naturally occurring catastrophic floods can take months to several years. The rate of such recolonization after flood recession will depend upon 1) how quick different species can disperse, 2) the presence of nearby “source populations” in unaffected areas, 3) unhindered connectivity between the impact zone and those source populations, and 4) the existence of suitable habitat in the river post-flood.

The wider impacts of the current conflict may have damaged potential “source populations” and habitat corridors through which species could recolonise areas affected by the flood.

Impacts on habitats and biodiversity on land:

Direct loss of terrestrial organisms: Many terrestrial organisms are likely to be killed by flooding (small mammals, invertebrates, reptiles) or have access to their breeding or feeding areas seriously disrupted at a time of year critical to their breeding cycles. Impacts are also likely across the food chain, even for species where adults can escape direct impacts (e.g. raptorial birds), if prey species are affected.

Impacts on habitats and biodiversity in the Black Sea:

Reductions in salinity: The Black Sea is effectively an enclosed water body with limited water exchange with the Mediterranean, meaning that tidal influence is minimal and salinity levels are relatively stable. The catastrophic floods reduced salinity of waters at the mouth of the Dniro from ~14ppt to ~4ppt (open oceans have an average salinity of 34-36ppt) with potential lethal or sub-lethal effects on marine organisms. However, the effects are likely to be temporary. Reductions in salinity along coastal habitats, including moist and wet dune slacks and saline coastal lagoons, are likely to be longer lasting.

Delivery of nutrients from upstream: Coastal deltas and estuaries are open systems with generally high critical load thresholds to nutrient additions, given the constant loading from upstream terrestrial and freshwater sources. However, marginal habitats such as coastal grassland and sand dunes are nutrient limited, and the impacts of additional nutrient loads deposited from the flood are likely to be significant, including for associated species. The combination of the hot summer and high nutrient loading can trigger blooms of microorganisms and algae leading to changes in water chemistry of coastal waters, impacting on human and environmental health.

4.3.4 UN hazard type & hazard cluster: geohazard – shallow geohazard

Impacts on habitats and biodiversity in Kakhovka Reservoir:

Increased sediment resuspension. Reservoir shallowing will make the remaining submerged sediments more vulnerable to resuspension. Given the shallow depth

and long fetch of the remaining reservoir, mixing energy will most likely be able to penetrate to the reservoir bed and cause the particles there to re-enter the water. Therefore, it is likely that the nutrients and other chemicals bound to the sediments could be resuspended into the reservoir, stimulating more phytoplankton (algal) growth, increasing the concentrations of pollutants, and deteriorating water quality. This effect could be exacerbated by inflowing waters. If it is assumed that water from upstream is released at its usual rate into the reservoir, there could be an increase in the concentrations of nutrients and other chemicals because those inflowing waters would be entering a much smaller volume than normal, and thus the dilution of inflowing nutrients and pollutants would be greatly reduced.

Impacts on habitats and biodiversity in the lower Dnipro River:

Scouring of in-channel habitats. High-velocity, catastrophic flood events will mobilise large debris (e.g. vegetation, large rocks, masonry from human infrastructures). Carried by high-energy flows, these materials will scour and destroy in-channel habitat patches that support aquatic organisms, such as submerged plant beds, emergent aquatic vegetation, bank overhangs, pools and riffles. Upon recession of the flood, the morphology of the Dnipro River channel is likely to be altered, with different numbers, areas, and spatial configurations of habitat patches. Several bird species nest in burrows in the banks of the Dnipro River, or in marginal vegetation. These nests and habitats will have been destroyed.

Impacts on habitats and biodiversity on land:

Sediment deposition. Floodwater is likely to contain high loads of sediments and pollutants, scoured from the reservoir bed and upstream reaches, as well as pollutants released directly by floodwater damage to infrastructure and storage systems. As floodwaters slow and recede, there is a high risk of deposition of these sediments and pollutants on terrestrial ecosystems. The affected regions are internationally important for both resident and breeding wildlife and as a migration corridor (Birdlife International estimates the total number of breeding waterbirds in the Dnipro Delta as 6,000-8,000 pairs, with over 140,000 waterbirds staging during migration).

Impacts on habitats and biodiversity in the Black Sea:

Habitat scouring and sediment deposition: Tide generating forces create tides within the Black Sea. The maximum tidal range varies from 1 cm near the Crimean Peninsula to 18–19 cm in the Dnipro–Bug Estuary. Radiational tides, initiated mainly

by sea breezes, also make an important contribution to the formation of tidal oscillations and in turn the formation of coastal and intertidal habitats. The high-velocity, catastrophic floods arising due to the dam breach could re-profile the coastline with unknown consequences for the extent and condition of coastal margin habitats and species. Deposition of large amounts of sediment is also likely, burying benthic species and habitats.

4.3.5 UN hazard type & hazard cluster: meteorological & hydrological – flood

Impacts on habitats and biodiversity in Kakhovka Reservoir:

Enhanced connectivity. An additional consequence of reduced reservoir water levels is that previously isolated island habitats could now be connected to the shore, and accessible to humans and natural predators (UNCG), 2023. As a result, we would expect disturbances to the behaviour (including breeding) of island-dwelling organisms, and a possibility of elevated mortality through predation. The example of The Archipelago Velyki and Mali Kuchugury Ramsar site within the reservoir illustrates the biodiversity importance of these islands, having a recorded 156 bird, 18 mammal, 54 fish, 867 insect, 163 plant, 14 algae, and 16 fungus species. Several bird species nest in these areas, including squacco heron (*Ardeola ralloides*), little egret (*Egretta garzetta*), Eurasian spoonbill (*Platalea leucorodia*), Eurasian oystercatcher (*Haematopus ostralegus*), and penduline tit (*Remiz pendulinus*). Of these species, the IUCN Red List of Threatened Species lists *H. ostralegus* as “vulnerable” at the European scale (with other species “least concern”).

Impacts on habitats and biodiversity on land:

Habitat inundation. Flooding in June is highly likely to disrupt the life cycles of many terrestrial species, including direct loss or damage of nests and offspring. Terrestrial habitats in the flooded areas downstream are composed mostly of herbaceous wetlands (around 35,000 Ha, 51% of the affected downstream area, ESA WorldCover 2021) in the Dnipro valley and delta. These wetlands are a mosaic of rivers, streams, pools, floodplain forests, swamps, reedbeds and sandbars. Although periodic flooding is part of the natural regime of wetland habitats, the velocity and depth of floodwater associated with the dam breach are likely to be extremely rare in nature. Additionally, natural flood regimes usually result in winter inundation, and wetland species time their life cycles accordingly. Flooding in June is thus highly likely to disrupt the life cycles of many terrestrial species, even where adult

individuals can escape or survive. This disruption includes direct loss or damage of nests and offspring, for example of birds nesting on the ground, (e.g. little gull *Hydrocoloeus minutus*, little bustard *Tetrax tetrax*) or in emergent vegetation. These examples breed in the affected area and are European red listed as “near threatened” or “vulnerable”. Disruption may also occur via the inundation of egg laying and larval emergence areas (e.g. dragonflies and damselflies), and by the prevention of access to feeding areas and disruption of the populations of aquatic prey species. Due to the atypical timing of the flooding, there is the potential for the loss of an entire year’s breeding output for many species – for short lived species such as many invertebrates, or species where local populations are already vulnerable, this may result in local extirpation. Flood pools in normally dry areas may, in some cases, help to alleviate the loss of wetland habitat, but only where species can move to exploit them. Such pools are also likely to be eutrophic and poorly oxygenated, and thus favour only a limited subset of aquatic species, including potentially problematic species such as mosquitoes.

For non-wetland habitats (e.g. grassland and woodland) the consequences of inundation are likely to be even more severe. Some 10,000 Ha of woodland and 11,000 Ha of grassland (ESA WorldCover 2021) are within the affected downstream area. Although many of the affected woodlands within the valley of the Dnipro are likely to be composed of species that can tolerate some level of flooding, the scale and intensity of flooding is likely to cause mechanical damage to trees, both directly and through soil erosion, and to cause further damage through waterlogging of tree roots. This latter issue is likely to be exacerbated by the timing of the flooding, when trees are actively growing, and oxygen demand is at its highest. Grasslands in the region are already known to be threatened by agricultural pollution and eutrophication, so further damage from flooding is likely to have severe consequences for local populations of species dependent on these habitats, such as the meadow viper (*Vipera ursinii*, European red listed as vulnerable). The region hosts several raptor species of conservation concern (e.g. *Circus cyaneus*, *Clanga*, *Falco cherrug*, *F. vespertinus*, European red listed as vulnerable or near threatened), which are likely to suffer from loss of access to their wetland and grassland foraging habitats and declines in populations of prey species.

As noted above, the current conflict may have damaged potential “source populations” and habitat corridors through which species could recolonise areas affected by the flood.

Impacts on habitats and biodiversity in the Black Sea:

Enhanced water mixing: The Black Sea is a meromictic basin, characterised by distinct layers of water at different densities (specifically, less-dense freshwater overlays denser saltwater). Exchanges between the two layers are limited, due to the density gradient, leading to a reduction or absence of oxygen at lower layers and a distinct ecology. The catastrophic floods could enable localised mixing and mobilisation of nutrients, and salinity exchanges from lower layers, impacting trophic links and food webs in surface layers. Furthermore, the mixing of fresh and saline water triggers the precipitation of nutrients and pollutants out of the water column with potentially lethal or sub-lethal consequences for all levels of the food chain, from plankton to cetaceans.

4.3.6 UN hazard type & hazard cluster: biological hazards – pathogenic microorganisms and toxins

An additional risk resulting from the dam breach, not included in the impact assessment on habitats, is related to the increase of pathogenic microorganisms and toxins in the Dnipro mouth and the Black Sea coastal waters. This may be caused by a combined effect of (i) flushing of solid and liquid wastes (e.g. sewage, toilet pits, manure) from inundated areas, (ii) decaying animals washed up in shallow waters, (iii) nutrient pollution and changes in salinity combined with high organic matter loading resulting in harmful algal blooms and pathogen accumulation in shallow waters. Anecdotal reports by the Sanitary and Epidemiological Service of Odesa region suggest an increase in the occurrence of salmonella and other gastro-intestinal infections in coastal waters in Odesa Bay and near Chornomorsk town following the dam breach. As of June 13th, 2023, incidences of intestinal diseases had increased 1.8 - 2.0 times in the Odesa region when compared to data prior to 7th June 2023.

4.3.7 Potential sources of radio-contaminants from Zaporizhzhia Nuclear Powerplant

This section falls outside our risk assessment of the Protected Areas, but we felt it would be useful to consider, given the potential risk posed by the nuclear powerplant situated on the shores of the reservoir. The Zaporizhzhia Nuclear Powerplant (ZNPP), one of the largest nuclear power plants in the world, is located approximately 145km upstream of the Kakhovka Dam. Operated by Energoatom, the ZNPP comprises six Russian-designed pressurised water (VVER-1000) reactors, a fresh fuel store and a large dry spent fuel storage facility; the fresh fuel store waste likely contains the isotopes ^{134}Cs , ^{137}Cs , ^{60}Co , ^{58}Co , ^{54}Mn , ^{124}Sb , ^{122}Sb , $^{110\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ and in

the high-level dry waste store there is likely a mix of alpha, beta and gamma emitting radionuclides (IAEA, 2022; Ukraine national report, 2017). All six of the reactors are currently in cold shutdown, which is the safest state for a reactor to be in.

Although the breach of the Kakhovka Dam does not pose a flooding risk to the ZNPP, it does have implications for the longer-term safety of this nuclear site. The ZNPP uses water from the adjacent cooling pond to remove residual heat from the reactors and used fuel ponds. Water losses from the cooling pond were replenished by water drawn from the Kakhovka Reservoir (IAEA 2006) however recent publications have stated onsite back-up options are available and are estimated to be sufficient for up to several months (OECD, 2023).

The sediments downstream of the ZNPP will contain radionuclides discharged from the plant during normal operations. Other sources of radioactive contaminants that may have been released into the flooded area could include: (i) radionuclides (e.g. ^{137}Cs and ^{90}Sr) that have been trapped in the lower sediments of the Kakhovka Reservoir following run-off from the Chernobyl accident (Kunkle & Khudov, 2023; Kaglyan, 1997) (ii) radionuclides used in hospitals for diagnostic and therapeutic applications (e.g. ^{99}Tc , ^{131}I , ^{125}I , ^{123}I ^{18}F and ^{14}C), sealed radioactive sources in scanning equipment and radionuclides awaiting disposal in holding tanks (Khan et al. 2010) and (iii) natural radionuclides associated with uranium mining (although there are no mines in or particularly close to the flooded area) that may be present in sediments (IAEA, 2006). There is also the potential that some radionuclides that were associated with lower sediments may now be closer to the surface and available for re-suspension (by water or air). The potential hazards from radioactive contaminants vary by emission type. Options for future assessment of radioactive contaminants are included in Section 5.0.

4.3.8 Potential sources of chemical pollutants

Sources of chemical pollutants (toxic and bioaccumulative substances and radionuclides) into the catchment downstream of the dam can be summarised as (i) pollutants dissolved in the water column of the Kakhovka Reservoir and associated with sediments (EUWI+, 2021) flushed from the Kakhovka Reservoir transported downstream of the dam with the floodwater movement; (ii) pollutants released from infrastructure at, and downstream of, the dam due to inundation by floodwaters. It is also possible that pollutants associated with sediments within the river channel downstream of the dam have been (re) mobilised due to sediment scouring by the floodwaters. As such, the flood waters are likely to contain a cocktail of pollutants, transported from the reservoir upstream of the Nova Kakhovka Dam and mobilized by the flood event downstream of the dam. The types of pollutants that may have been mobilized are dependent on the nature of affected infrastructure downstream of

the dam, and the pollution history of the upstream reservoir, which will have controlled the types and concentrations of pollutants present in the sediments. Table 4.1 provides a general summary of the types of pollutants that may be mobilized from different flooded pollution sources.

Table 4.1. Summary of potential pollutants associated with different infrastructure sources within the flood zone

Infrastructure sources	Potential pollutants
Hydroelectric installations	Industrial lubricants (which may contain components such as metals, PCBs, organic additives in addition to main oil component), and contaminated bed sediments
Wastewater treatment plants	Raw domestic and industrial sewage, surfactants and personal care products
Harbour / shipping facilities	Fuel, engine oils, industrial lubricants, antifouling biocides, fertilisers, bulk industrial chemicals
Factories/industrial units	Metals, oils/waxes including fuel oils and lubricants, solvents, site specific chemicals used in production
Landfill sites	Plastics, plasticisers, surfactants, biocidal products, pharmaceuticals, industrial POPs e.g. PDBEs, polyaromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), pesticides and their degradation products, personal care products, metals, organic biological waste
Fuel stations	Fuel, lubricant oils
Human settlements	Human waste, lubricant oils, plastics, metals, asbestos (from building materials), personal care products, surfactants, antibacterials, pharmaceuticals and radionuclides (from e.g. hospitals), biological waste
Farming	Animal slurry, oils, fuel, fertilisers, antibacterials, pesticides, fungicides, biological waste from animals, pathogens (e.g. anthrax spores from carcasses), asbestos (from building materials)
Airports	Fuel, oils, lubricants, fire retardants
Mining	Heavy metals, arsenic, coal and oil associated hydrocarbons, PAHs, iron oxides, natural radionuclides
Nuclear power plants, nuclear waste storage facilities	Radionuclides, Chernobyl deposition
Military	Mines, fuel oils, explosive compounds

Pollutants in the water column and sediment of the Kakhovka Reservoir and downstream river

The dam creates a natural barrier in the river that reduces flow and will allow the settling of sediments transported downstream. Pollutants from industrial sources and sewage effluent that are released upstream of the dam, and which are preferentially associated with sediment, will accumulate through deposition in the reservoir. Following the breach, this sediment will be mobilized and transported downstream, as will any pollutants in the water column. This potential for pollutant export can be illustrated by considering the hydraulic retention time of the reservoir (an estimate of how long it would take, in days, for all water in the reservoir to be replaced). Assuming a Kakhovka Reservoir volume of 18.18 km^3 and a mean daily run-off of $2,600 \text{ m}^3$, we can estimate that the typical retention time was approximately 81 days. Immediately following the dam's destruction, the run-off was estimated at $30,000 \text{ m}^3$, yielding a retention time of only 7 days. If we further assume that the "useful" volume of the reservoir above 12.7 m has now been lost (estimated at 6.78 m^3) and the flow into Kakhovka Reservoir is maintained at something approximating the normal daily mean run-off (i.e., $2,600 \text{ m}^3$), the new estimated retention time could now be 51 days. In a Facebook message on 11 June, the Ukrainian Meteorological Center reported that the reservoir had lost 73% of its volume, leaving only 5.4 km^3 . Such a volume would result in a retention time of only 24 days, and levels more typical of a large river. This change could greatly increase pollutant and nutrient export downstream by reducing the potential for deposition of sediment and associated nutrients/pollutants.

As the flood progresses and the water spreads, the reduction in flow will allow the polluted sediment to settle. As the flood water recedes, this will leave behind a new surface layer of sediment across the flooded area. The pollutants associated with this layer of deposited material will mirror those present in the reservoir sediment and overlying water at the time that the breach occurred. Because of the long residence time expected for sediments in the Kakhovka Reservoir, any pollutants released from upstream sources that are readily broken down will have had sufficient time to be degraded. This will mean such pollutants may be at relatively low concentrations in sediment, although they may be present in the overlying water. The pollutants that are present in sediment will be dominated by those substances that have a relatively long half-life in the system such as trace elements, including cadmium lead, mercury and arsenic, radionuclides, persistent organic pollutants, including PCBs, PDBEs, dioxin and PFAS compounds, and persistent coal associated hydrocarbons and PAHs. For some of the floodwater, the downstream flow will continue to the point where the water enters the Black Sea. Polluted sediment and water carried by this flow will ultimately be deposited into the, mainly coastal, areas in a plume that spreads from the mouth of the river. As the flow

subsides the extent of this plume will decrease and deposition will occur closer to the river mouth, with the estuary region a specific hotspot for deposition because of tidal back-up and salinity change, which both encourage sediment settling.

Pollutants released from infrastructure due to inundation by floodwaters

The impacts of pollutants released from infrastructure will depend on both the scale of release and also the nature of the chemicals involved. From a risk assessment perspective, chemical pollutant releases can have both direct toxic effects on the species exposed and also, by accumulating in trophic networks (food webs), can cause effects on other species that are themselves not directly exposed. The duration of these effects will depend on the persistence of the pollutant chemical. Some more labile substances will be rapidly (weeks-months, months-years) broken down by biotic and abiotic reactions, while others will be recalcitrant and may remain, contaminating the affected ecosystems for extended periods (years-decades). The relative risks of the different pollutants that are likely to have been released as a result of flooding can be categorized for their potential to cause impacts both directly and through bioaccumulation, as well as the potential longevity of those effects (Table 4.2). This information on hazard and potential exposure duration can be used to calculate the potential impact of chemical release from an infrastructure facility which will be the product of the scale of release, the direct toxicity and bioaccumulation potential of the chemical, and the persistence of those released chemicals.

Table 4.2. Summary of pollutant hazard potential and persistence for risk assessment profiling of sources

Pollutant	Direct toxicity/ effect hazard	Bioaccumulation hazard	Environmental persistence
Cadmium	High	High	Long
Lead	Medium	Medium	Long
Mercury	High	High	Long
Arsenic	Medium	Medium	Long
Other trace metals	Medium	Low	Long
Radionuclides	High	Medium	Long
Fuel oils	High	Low	Short
Lubricant oils	Medium	Low	Intermediate
Coal hydrocarbons	Low	Low	Long
PAHs	Medium	Medium	Intermediate
POPs (PCBs, PBDEs, Dioxins, PFAS)	Medium	High	Long
Fertilisers	Low	Low	Long
Pesticide and biocides	High	Medium	Short
Pharmaceuticals	High	Medium	Short
Surfactants / personal care products	Medium	Medium	Intermediate
Solvents	High	Low	Short
Industrial chemicals (including plasticisers)	Medium	Medium	Intermediate
Plastics	Low	Low	Long
Asbestos	Low	Low	Long
Explosives	High	Low	Intermediate
Biowastes and sewage	Medium	Low	Intermediate
Pathogens	High	Low	Long

After initial release, the nature and area affected will be driven by a range of spatial transport and temporal fate and exposure processes. As a result of these processes, the pattern of pollution and the hazards that will result from the dam breach and resulting flooding can be expected to play out across time and space.

4.4 Rapid environmental risk assessment approach

Expert assessment of the above hazards for all Protected Areas are presented in Table 4.3. Our assessment shows that the relative risk of significant impacts from each hazard vary greatly among ecosystems distributed along the upstream – downstream continuum. In general, we assess organism mortality (through stranding and direct loss), habitat drying (through emersion at lower water levels), and enhanced connectivity (through connecting islands to the shore) to be the greatest risks to biodiversity in the Kakhovka Reservoir and ten associated Protected Areas.

In downstream river terrestrial and coastal ecosystems, our assessment suggests that organism mortality (through direct loss and immersion), habitat inundation within the flood zone, short-term and long-term effects from pollution (especially in the vicinity of major industrial infrastructure) and re-shaping of the river system through enhanced erosion and sediment deposition could have significant impacts upon biodiversity, ecosystem structure and function in a further ten habitat areas.

For this study, this risk assessment has only focused on the initial impact of the dam breach. Whilst some of the identified hazards are severe for many of the 21 habitats examined, we have not considered the recovery or long-term impact of these hazards due to the limitation of time and information in assembling this report. We would strongly recommend that such a factor is considered in a future study.

There is a possibility of significant and ongoing impacts associated with the exposure of organisms to mobilised pollutants. These impacts may result from the movement of existing polluted sediments, and the release of new pollution due to impacts on infrastructure. In the immediate aftermath, areas around and downstream of the point of release are likely to experience the highest chemical concentrations and potential impacts. Petrochemical production and distribution sites (which may release long-chain hydrocarbons and PAHs), industrial facilities (which may release solvents, industrial chemicals, and metals), and chemical stores (such as for agrochemicals) are likely hotspots for such potential effects. As the pollutants move downstream, pollutants will tend to accumulate in area of high sedimentation. Within these hotspots, some of the more labile chemicals potentially present will degrade. However, more long-lived chemicals, such as metals and persistent organics, may pose significant challenges in these areas, not only for directly exposed species, but also for predators via food chain transfer.

Table 4.3 Expert opinion risk assessment matrix for environmental hazards resulting from the Nova Kakhovka Dam breach

Risk rating

not relevant	low	medium	high
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UN Office for Disaster Risk Reduction Hazard Definitions

Hazard type		Biological	Chemical			Environmental					Geohazard			Meteorological & Hydrological			
Hazard cluster		Aquaculture	Toxic substances	Bioaccumulative substances	Radionuclides	Environmental degradation					Shallow geohazard			Flood			
Ecological target	Habitat type	Growth of "algal" blooms	Direct toxic effects on wildlife	Sustained effects on higher trophic levels and food quality	Direct toxic effects on wildlife, human exposure	Stranding of organisms	Direct loss of organisms	Emersion of habitats	Salinity reduction	Downstream nutrient enrichment/eutrophication	Sediment resuspension	Habitat scouring	Sediment deposition	Enhanced connectivity	Enhanced water mixing	Habitat inundation	
Ecosystem	Kakhovka Reservoir	Reservoir (Emerald Network)															
	Zaplava r. Bazavluk	River feeding Kakhovka Reservoir north (Zakaznik)															
	Archipelago Velyki and Mali Kuchuguri	Sandbar islands in Kakhovka Reservoir (RAMSAR)															
	Veliki ta Mali Kuchuguri	Island system Kakhovka Reservoir (Zakaznik)															
	Sim Maiakiv Floodplain	Floodplain forests, wet meadows and reed beds within Kakhovka Reservoir (RAMSAR)															
	Lisoviy masiv	Wetland east Kakhovka Reservoir (Zakaznik)															
	Velykyi Luh	Wetland component on south shore of Kakhovka Reservoir (Emerald Network)															
	Urochische Maygora	Lake (Zakaznik)															
	Vodyans'ki Kuchuguri	Wetland on south shore of Kakhovka Reservoir (Zakaznik)															
	Kam'yans'kiy lisoviy masiv	Freshwater coastal forest (Zakaznik)															
	Ivanivs'kiy bar	Wetland on south shore of Kakhovka Reservoir (Zakaznik)															
	Downstream Dnipro	Lowland River (Emerald Network)															
	Lower Inhulets river valley	River (Emerald Network)															
	Oleshkivski Pisky	Desert (Emerald Network)															
	Dnipro River Delta	River /lake/floodplain forests (RAMSAR)															
	Kinburnska Kosa	Coastal spit (Emerald Network)															
	Dniprovska-Buzkyi Lyman	Coastal/Marine Protected Area (Emerald Network)															
	Biloberezhzhia Sviatoslava	Peninsula of Dnipro-Buh estuary (Emerald Network)															
	Loess outcrops of the Dnipro estuary	Coastal (Emerald Network)															
	Black Sea Biosphere Reserve	Marine (Emerald Network)															
Chernomorskiy	Coastal islands/sand bars/wetland (UNESCO-MAB Biosphere Reserve)																

5.0 Strategic review of a range of other impacts associated with the Nova Kakhovka Dam breach [Component 4]

The rapid analysis presented in the components above was conducted within a period of two weeks. It describes the hazard caused by the breach of the Nova Kakhovka Dam analysing the flood hydrology, hydraulics and sediment transport. Following identification of the hazard, the impact is assessed on land cover and flooded infrastructure, irrigation, species, habitats, and sources of potential pollution. A risk-based assessment approach is developed and applied including hazard classification and a preliminary risk assessment from species to river basin scales.

Component 4 presents a strategic review of a range of other impacts associated with the Nova Kakhovka Dam breach which are possible with further analysis over additional time and benefitting from additional supporting data. This includes considerations of wider impacts of similar events in upstream dams and other dams in eastern Ukraine. We identify areas for further assessment which will be important in assisting decision-making around prioritisation and implementation of disaster recovery actions. These studies are designed to inform, where relevant, short term emergency response actions as well as longer term planning for reconstruction.

5.1 Key findings

Ten potential impact topics have been identified:

- Topic 1: Assessment of the potential impacts of the failure of other dams
- Topic 2: Flood risk to the Zaporizhzhia Nuclear Powerplant from upstream dam breaches
- Topic 3: Impacts on water infrastructure, quality, and supply
- Topic 4: Lower Dnipro River waterway transport
- Topic 5: Potential sources of radioactive contaminants following the Nova Kakhovka Dam breach
- Topic 6: Change in overall flood risk downstream of Dnipro Dam
- Topic 7: Risk from munitions dispersal in lower Dnipro River
- Topic 8: Physical and chemical impacts on the Black Sea

Topic 9: Constructing recovery plans for species and habitats of high conservation, cultural, and commercial interest

Topic 10: Extending risk analysis from 'plausible' to 'realised' risk assessment

Two other possible impact studies were suggested, but have not been developed in any more detail:

- Further breaching of the Nova Kakhovka Dam: not developed owing to the need for information unlikely to be available in the expected timescales for this analysis;
- Hydropower operations: not developed since it would require other expertise to assess.

Note that there would be efficiencies in performing a combination of certain of these tasks, since they would rely upon similar preparatory work and modelling to perform the analysis in each case.

5.2 Background and approach

The project Terms of Reference included an appendix giving a list of eight other strategic impacts of the Nova Kakhovka Dam breach which were possibilities for further analysis. These have been developed, refined and re-framed into the list given here through consultation with appropriate specialists at HR Wallingford and UKCEH. Two topics were removed due to their need for expertise and information unavailable in this team, or because of evidence suggesting they are no longer relevant.

A brief commentary describing each potential impact is given, followed by: a description of the precise products that would be produced by the recommended analyses; the associated confidence in these products should the analysis be required to be completed in a short timescale; and the messages that would result from such an analysis.

The underpinning issues and recommendations on data and evidence sharing with the international community are as follows:

- There is a need for improved information and data availability which could be resolved by a data sharing agreement with the Ukrainian Government.
- Several Ukrainian research institutes have valuable capabilities and knowledge, and facilitation of bi-lateral agreements would aid in the analysis.
- At least one other review of environmental impacts has been conducted (i.e., by Finland). A coordinated international scientific response through

bi-lateral knowledge sharing could be explored to increase confidence in impact assessments.

- During the preparation of this report, we were made aware of an evidence review on the Kakhovka Dam breach being led by the United Nations Environment Programme Conflicts and Disasters Branch, to conclude mid-July. This report may be useful in informing this UNEP assessment.

5.3 List of potential impacts for future assessments

5.3.1 Topic 1: Assessment of the potential impacts of the failure of other dams

Figure 5.1 shows 13 other dams in Eastern Ukraine together with those five remaining in the Dnipro River cascade above Nova Kakhovka. They have been identified from the International Commission on Large Dams (ICOLD) World Register of Dams (ICOLD, undated) and their positions derived from the information on the associated river and nearest town.

Each of the dams along the Dnipro River has a reservoir area above 400km², with Kremenchuk and Kyiv above 900km². Indeed, the area of the reservoir above the Kremenchuk Dam is comparable to that of the Nova Kakhovka Dam. Certain impacts associated with this cascade of dams have been discussed elsewhere in this report. In addition to these specific impacts, breaching of any of these five dams would potentially have wide-ranging impacts, some of a similar magnitude to those of the Nova Kakhovka Dam.

Other large dams in Eastern Ukraine from the World Register of Dams are numbered 1 to 13 in Figure 5.1 in descending order of reservoir area. An article in *The Guardian* (Borger and Sabbagh, 2023) gives an unverified report of another dam at Klyuchove (not given in the ICOLD World Register of Dams) on the Mokri Yaly River being destroyed.

The dam at point 3 is on the Luhanka River near the town of Svitlodarsk, with a reservoir area of 21km². According to Google Maps/Earth there is a power station alongside the reservoir and two more immediately downstream. The dam at point 4 is on the Kalmius River near the town of Starobesheve, with a reservoir area of 12 km². There appears to be a quarry or mine workings downstream, carrying a potential contamination risk. Both dams are in the area currently controlled by Russia. Four of the dams given in Figure 5.1 are in Crimea.

We propose an impact and disaster risk reduction analysis, following the R-EIA approach developed here, of breach scenarios in other dams, with priority being potentially determined by the live reservoir volume/length and dam height (which will inform the attenuation of the outflow hydrograph) and the number of important receptors (such as urbanised areas; ecosystems of high conservation status; key infrastructure including drinking water supply) downstream:

- **Deliverables:** Hydraulic models and environmental risk analyses of dam breach scenarios giving flood extents, velocities and depths, and impacts across the Impact Indicator Framework and Hazards Categorisation Frameworks developed above. Similar impact studies to those given in this report are possible for these scenarios, depending on the local circumstances. In addition, dynamic agent-based models can be run to assess potential risk to life.
- **Confidence in results:** Confidence in the hydraulic models is high owing to the established nature of the models and the skills developed at HR Wallingford; confidence in the wider impact studies is at least moderate given the GIS Products developed here on Impact Indicators and Hazard Classification Framework although availability of supporting data from within Ukraine would increase confidence to high. Confidence in the risk-to-life models is moderate owing to variations in population estimates since the start of the war.
- **Resulting messages:** Potential resulting messages are similar to those from the studies conducted in Components 1, 2 and 3, excepting the impact to the Black Sea. The risk-to-life models produce risk of fatalities and injuries from the flood inundation and emergency management interventions to reduce this risk. Assessing Disaster Reduction Scenarios in accordance with the UN Disaster Risk Reduction Programme could support coordinated international assessments.
- **Relevance to impact assessment and disaster recovery:** The proposed activities will identify areas of greatest environmental risk to future potential dam losses. The approach should underpin the preparation of risk reduction measures that could be implemented, for example, with respect to key infrastructure for drinking water, important pollutant sources (e.g. upstream chemical waste containment reservoirs). It may also include measures to protect biodiversity through increasing species distribution corridors or establishing translocation programmes or refuge habitats. The risk-to-life models produce risk of fatalities and injuries and the potential for emergency management intervention to reduce this risk. Assessing Disaster Reduction Scenarios in accordance with the UN Disaster Risk Reduction Programme could support coordinated international assessments.

Figure 5.1 Large dams along the Dnipro River up to Kyiv (named) and in Eastern Ukraine (numbered in descending order of reservoir area). Note we assume what is referred to as ‘Zaporizhzhia’ in this image is the Dnipro Dam at Zaporizhzhia.

5.3.2 Topic 2: Flood risk to the Zaporizhzhia Nuclear Powerplant from upstream dam breaches

The Zaporizhzhia Nuclear Powerplant (ZNPP), one of the largest nuclear power plants in the world, lies about 145km upstream of the Nova Kakhovka Dam, on the south bank of the Kakhovka Reservoir. Online photos indicate that it is situated at a level not much higher than the pre-breach level of the reservoir. If the Dnipro Dam upstream is breached then this would cause a flood wave, the height of which would depend on the size and location of the breach. The volume of the Dnipro Reservoir is considerably less than that of the Kakhovka Reservoir but a breach in the Dnipro Dam would produce a dynamic flood wave resulting in a larger increase in water level. Furthermore, the situation would be much more serious if the cascade of dams above the Zaporizhzhia powerplant failed. This might occur if a dam further upstream failed producing a flood wave causing failures of the dams further downstream.

As a separate case from the assessments of the impacts of the failure of the dams given above, we recommend a specific flood risk analysis of the Zaporizhzhia Nuclear Powerplant from breaches in the upstream dam(s).

- **Deliverables:** Flood risk analysis of the Zaporizhzhia Nuclear Powerplant using a hydraulic model to produce flood extents, depths and velocities for a set of breach scenarios.
- **Confidence in results:** Moderate, benefiting from established models and skills developed at HR Wallingford and requiring testing of a set of scenarios. Would benefit from Dnipro River surveys.
- **Resulting messages:** Risk of flooding to the Zaporizhzhia Nuclear Powerplant from worst case and reasonable likely scenarios of dam breaches upstream.
- **Relevance to impact assessment and disaster recovery:** Risk of flooding to the Zaporizhzhia Nuclear Powerplant from worst case and reasonable likely scenarios of dam breaches upstream. This assessment will provide scenarios of future altered hydrological systems with which to plan for mitigation measures and identify worst case scenarios for the safe operational conditions of the plant.

5.3.3 Topic 3: Impacts on water infrastructure, quality and supply

There is a high likelihood that drinking water infrastructure has been damaged or disrupted as a result of initial flooding/inundation and changing water levels and raw water quality. Damage is likely to have been caused to water treatment plants, service reservoirs, pumping stations and the distribution network in general, affecting the amount of drinking water available and its quality. Similarly, wastewater (sewage) treatment works and the sewerage network may have been damaged, which could result in untreated wastewater and sewage entering the environment and becoming a risk to human health. The UN reported that supply to up to 700,000 people may have been disrupted because of the Nova Kakhovka Dam failure (see also the BBC News article from 23 June 2023; Harding, 2023). We draw attention here to the risk of legacy water contamination because of the changing hydrological function of the Kakhovka Reservoir. Lowering of water levels may lead to enhanced deoxygenation and disturbance of legacy pollutants which in turn may liberate contaminants from bed sediments to surface waters, representing a human health risk. Contemporary pollutant sources including from munitions may also be important. Human-health risk via microbial contamination of fresh/coastal waters and via consumption of contaminated aquatic products should also be considered. The analysis in this report shows that the lowering of reservoir levels has affected the water supply to the Crimean Peninsula and irrigated agriculture between the Crimea and the Kakhovka Reservoir, since key irrigation canals are no longer being supplied with water. A loss of water supply to upstream connected canal systems may disrupt water supply for

drinking water and agriculture. In the longer term, alternative water supplies may be feasibly provided to towns, cities and agricultural areas from new abstraction points upstream and downstream of the Nova Kakhovka Dam and from groundwater sources. An assessment of change in reservoir yield would also assist with understanding the amount of water available in the system. We propose an analysis of immediate and longer-term impacts on the water supply network in the upstream and downstream impact zone towards identifying mitigation options to inform food and water security recovery.

The Zaporizhzhia Nuclear Power Plant (ZNPP) uses water from the adjacent cooling pond to remove residual heat from the reactors and used fuel ponds. Water losses from the cooling pond used to be replenished by water drawn from the Kakhovka Reservoir. However, recent publications have stated onsite back-up options are available and are estimated to be sufficient for up to several months. Further analysis of this situation is required.

- **Deliverables:** Short-term impacts on water supply and connection and assessment of potential contamination and associated human health risk across the drinking water supply network providing evidence to support recovery and reconstruction scenarios. Potential options for mitigating water stress caused by the dam breach, including locations of new abstraction points and potential areas for groundwater sources to replace surface water abstractions impacted by the breach.
- **Confidence in results:** Moderate – high, benefitting from any river survey data that can be made available pre- or post-breach, as well as locations of drinking water treatment and supply works. Confidence could be improved where suitable calibration data could be obtained.
- **Resulting messages:** Identification of water supply disruption and water quality risk maps to support longer-term recovery planning. Identification of alternative water supplies which could be provided to towns and cities (e.g. from groundwater or abstraction from further upstream), and to support drinking water asset planning and agriculture.
- **Relevance to impact assessment and disaster recovery:** Identification of water supply disruption and water quality risk maps to support recovery planning within the constraints of new hydrological scenarios (e.g., current hydrological status and through dam rebuilding phases) are essential. In the immediate response phase, this work would allow identification of alternative water supplies which could be provided to towns and cities or to support evacuation routes or for cooling at the ZNPP. In the longer term reconstruction/rebuilding phase the proposed work will identify suitable locations for new installations including

through assessments of security and raw water quality stress on drinking water asset planning and irrigation for agriculture.

5.3.4 Topic 4: Lower Dnipro River waterway transport

The Dnipro River is a major artery for the export of grain. Downstream of the Nova Kakhovka Dam, the Dnipro River levels and flows are no longer being controlled by dam operations. The lock in the Nova Kakhovka Dam is almost certainly out of action. The release of sediment when the dam was breached, and the reduced flow control, may result in reduced water depths downstream of the dam. We propose an analysis of the impact of the Nova Kakhovka Dam breach on the lower Dnipro River waterway transport capability:

- **Deliverables:** Short-term effects on water transport in key areas of changed waterway characteristics.
- **Confidence in results:** Moderate – high, benefitting from any river survey data that can be made available pre- or post-breach.
- **Resulting messages:** Identification of navigation pinch-points needing urgent intervention such as dredging or aids to navigation (e.g. channel marks). Can also inform longer-term planning of remedial measures for maintaining the waterway for grain shipment.
- **Relevance to impact assessment and disaster recovery:** This task will deliver revised navigation risk maps focussing on sediment distribution and the new hydrological regime of the system. This will be presented relative to pre-impact conditions with a focus on heavily utilised navigation channels and typical craft in use there. Navigation pinch-points will be identified that require urgent intervention such as dredging or aids to navigation (e.g. channel marks). This work will also inform longer-term planning of remedial measures for maintaining the waterway for grain shipment.

5.3.5 Topic 5: Potential sources of radioactive contaminants following the Nova Kakhovka Dam breach

The Zaporizhzhia Nuclear Powerplant (ZNPP) comprises six Russian-designed pressurised water (VVER-1000) reactors, a fresh fuel store and a large dry spent fuel storage facility; the fresh fuel store waste likely contains the isotopes ^{134}Cs , ^{137}Cs , ^{60}Co , ^{58}Co , ^{54}Mn , ^{124}Sb , ^{122}Sb , and $^{110\text{m}}\text{Ag}$. In the high-level dry waste store there is likely a mix of alpha, beta and gamma emitters. All six of the reactors are currently in cold shutdown, which is the safest state for a reactor to be in.

The breach of the Nova Kakhovka Dam has implications for the longer-term safety of this nuclear site. The ZNPP uses water from the adjacent cooling pond to remove residual heat from the reactors and used fuel ponds. Water losses from the cooling pond were replenished by water drawn from the Kakhovka Reservoir however recent publications have stated onsite back-up options are available and are estimated to be sufficient for up to several months (OECD, 2023). As discussed above, any breach of upstream dams, specifically the Dnipro Dam may also have implications for the safe operation of the ZNPP.

The sediments downstream of the ZNPP will contain radionuclides discharged from the plant during normal operations. Other sources of radioactive contaminants that may have been released into the flooded area could include: (i) radionuclides (e.g. ^{137}Cs and ^{90}Sr) that have been trapped in the lower sediments of the Kakhovka Reservoir (confirmed in the literature for this region) following run-off from the Chernobyl accident (ii) radionuclides used in hospitals for diagnostic and therapeutic applications (e.g. ^{99}Tc , ^{131}I , ^{125}I , ^{123}I , ^{18}F and ^{14}C), sealed radioactive sources in scanning equipment and radionuclides awaiting disposal in holding tanks and (iii) natural radionuclides associated with uranium mining (although there are no mines in or particularly close to the flooded area) that may be present in sediments. There is also the potential that some radionuclides that were associated with lower sediments may now be closer to the surface and available for re-suspension (by water or air).

We propose using measured or estimated media (water, sediment, soil) activity concentrations to conduct a radiological dose assessment for wildlife (e.g. birds, mammals, fish, amphibians and molluscs etc.) targeting impacted terrestrial, freshwater and marine ecosystems using the [ERICA Tool](#). The Tool is likely the most widely used model worldwide for estimation of radiological risk.

- **Deliverables:** Assessment of risk of exposure to radioactive pollutants associated with legacy and potential contemporary pollution sources in terrestrial, freshwater and coastal ecosystems. This work will inform long-term impact surveillance as conducted following the Chernobyl incident.
- **Confidence in results:** High - owing to the established nature of the models and the skills and track record at UKCEH and University of Salford. Confidence in modelling could be strengthened following post-conflict surveillance of impact zones. The team draw on decades of experience in monitoring the impacts of radioactive pollutants and interactions with the environment (e.g. Chernobyl exclusion zone and wider impacts) across multiple ecosystem types.
- **Resulting messages:** That radioactive pollutants have or have not been mobilised following the Nova Kakhovka Dam breach representing a long-term potential risk to wildlife.

- **Relevance to impact assessment and disaster recovery:** The proposed work will examine the risk to the environment posed by mobilisation of radioactive pollutants following the Nova Kakhovka Dam breach. Such pollutants are highly likely to be in the bed sediments of the system from historical events including Chernobyl Disaster and through waste disposal related to the Zaporizhzhya Nuclear Powerplant, as well as from other sources. Risk maps and ecotoxicological exposure and effects will be mapped and designed to underpin remediation efforts, potentially including sediment remediation and removal from hot spots of pollutant deposition. These outputs should consider scenarios developed and outlined above for flood risk and cessation of cooling water on the Zaporizhzhya Nuclear Powerplant.

5.3.6 Topic 6: Change in overall flood risk downstream of Dnipro Dam

The flow of the Dnipro River is no longer controlled by Nova Kakhovka Dam. Although the dam did not have a specific flood control purpose, due to the nature of its shape and size, it had an impact on the flow regime of the Dnipro River. The upstream cascade of dams is still in place so there is continued flow control and flood attenuation from those structures, notably from Dnipro Dam. A high-level analysis of the change in overall flood risk in the river downstream of Dnipro Dam has been presented in Section 2.0.

We recommend a more detailed flood risk analysis, which would look at the changed flood hazard and risk downstream (before and after the dam breach), as well as investigating other potential seasonal flow changes in the river system downstream.

- **Deliverables:** Flood risk assessment and hydrological assessment derived from analysis of the lower Dnipro River and the changed flood regime due to loss of Nova Kakhovka Dam.
- **Confidence in results:** Moderate to High owing to flood risk expertise of HR Wallingford, limited by the availability of observed historical flow data and knowledge of the operation of the cascade of five remaining upstream dams.
- **Resulting messages:** Flood risk assessment for key assets downstream of the Dnipro Dam to support the development of flood mitigation measures.
- **Relevance to impact assessment and disaster recovery:** Flood risk assessment for key assets downstream of the Dnipro Dam should be produced to support the development of flood mitigation measures in the short term, prior to reconstruction efforts, to protect exposed communities and infrastructure. New flood risk mapping would underpin future reconstruction efforts to establish where extreme events will likely impact new infrastructure developments using future scenarios of dam installation versus current hydrological conditions. This

approach will also underpin assessment of habitat quality and suitability for high conservation status species in line with conservation designations.

5.3.7 Topic 7: Risk from munitions dispersal in lower Dnipro River

If mines or other explosives were present in the Nova Kakhovka Dam when it breached, or in the surrounding catchments in the flood zone, then they may represent several specific risks to the downstream environment. These risks may include transport during surge of unexploded devices into navigation zones, emersion within downstream habitats following flood recession, and burying by redeposition of mobilised material. Evidence of contemporary pollution from munitions and heavy industry (i.e., elevated levels of mercury, vanadium, cadmium, non-radioactive strontium, elevated gamma-radiation) have been reported in bed sediment samples collected in 2017 from other reservoirs in Ukraine (i.e., Karlivske and Kleban-Bytske Reservoirs, Donetsk Oblast, Ukraine; OSCE, 2017). We propose a dispersal study to identify parts of the system where mobilisation and movement of mines is most likely. A chemical risk assessment is also proposed to screen potential contaminants associated with munitions and their short- and long-term impacts on biodiversity and human health (i.e., through consumption of contaminated food).

- **Deliverables:** Plots showing areas at high risk of containing transported / buried munitions.
- **Confidence in results:** Moderate, requiring use of thresholds to communicate risk.
- **Resulting messages:** Prediction of land areas at high risk of exposure / release of buried munitions. Could support contingency planning for other dam failures regarding munitions disturbance, together with additional information on safe navigation on the lower Dnipro River.
- **Relevance to impact assessment and disaster recovery:** An assessment of land areas at high risk of exposure / release of buried munitions is necessary to establish the extent of this risk. This work would support contingency planning for other dam failures regarding munitions disturbance, together with additional information on safe navigation on the lower Dnipro River. In addition, it would allow identification of potential hot spots of pollution associated with munitions over the longer term detailing exposure risk to specific species and habitats.

5.3.8 Topic 8: Physical and chemical impacts on the Black Sea

Reports indicate that the release of water from Kakhovka Reservoir has altered the salinity along the northern coast of the Black Sea. The Black Sea is a meromictic ecosystem, meaning that it consists of a bottom layer of anoxic saline water overlain

by a freshwater layer. These two layers do not mix under normal conditions. The sudden input of freshwater to the system may have disrupted the stability of this mixing regime, at least locally. Consequences of introducing salt water to freshwater environments should be considered further. The water released in the flood surge may have introduced pollutants and debris into the Black Sea. The transport pathways, composition and longer-term impacts of pollutants and debris require further assessment. Further work is proposed to understand the physical impacts of freshwater inputs and changes in salinity on the mixing regime of the receiving waters. The likely passage and collection points of the pollutants and debris from the dam break and their potential impact on biodiversity also require further assessment, for example, informed using a wave / flow model for the Black Sea.

- **Deliverables:** Assessment showing the extent of freshwater and pollution dispersal from the mouth of the Dnipro River and impacts on physical mixing, as well as the extent of floating object dispersal from the mouth of the Dnipro River including possible areas of landfall.
- **Confidence in results:** High, using established techniques of water flow and pollutant transport, and moderate for debris tracking and physical mixing owing to uncertainties associated with the size and density of buoyant debris and validation of physical mixing models.
- **Resulting messages:** Coastal and marine areas at risk from water pollution, freshwater input, and floating and washed-up debris.
- **Relevance to impact assessment and disaster recovery:** The impacts of pollutants mobilised and transported to the Black Sea coastal habitats is unclear. This work will establish the extent to which coastal and marine areas are at risk from water pollution, freshwater input, and floating and washed-up debris associated with the Kakhovka Dam breach.

5.3.9 Topic 9: Recovery plans for species and habitats of high conservation, cultural and commercial interest

In addition to agriculture, the Nova Kakhovka Dam and downstream Dnipro River to the Black Sea are important for a wide range of sensitive and protected species (Section 2.0) and recovery plans are required for some of these. No assessment of long-term habitat recovery has been included in this report and we would recommend such analysis in a future study. Although this analysis should be extended to target species of high conservation or cultural/commercial interest, we present, here, an example narrative focussing on fish.

Kakhovka Reservoir was the habitat for about 43 fish species, of which 20 species have commercial value (annual catches amounted to about 2,600 tonnes).

Unconfirmed reports citing estimates from the Ukraine State Fisheries Agency suggest that 28,000 crucian carp were lost following the dam failure; estimates for potential total losses reaching 95,000 tonnes with a commercial value of USD 108 million for mature fish.

Two fish-breeding hatcheries are situated downstream of the Nova Kakhovka Dam. Firstly, the Kherson production-experimental plant which produces annually 13.4 million individuals of commercial fish species (e.g. carp, pike, zander, catfish, bream, walleye, white carp). Secondly, there is the Dnipro Sturgeon Fish Breeding Plant which is designed to produce 2.6 million fry of commercial species of fish. This includes sturgeon (1.6 million fry) which were to stock upstream reservoirs. It has been estimated by Ukrainian sources that the loss of just the sturgeon is worth UAH 900 million (£19 million). These sources of stocking are vital in maintaining fish populations in the reservoirs that currently block the natural movement of such species.

We propose that species-specific recovery plans be developed to aid in wider disaster recovery planning. These assessments should consider the life-histories, habitat requirements, and sensitivity to environmental change of the species including scenarios of long-term habitat reconstruction required following the Nova Kakhovka Dam failure, and in the context of the R-EIA presented in this report. An assessment of red list or high commercial value species should be conducted to inform prioritisation of this analysis.

- **Deliverables:** Assessment of impacts pathways for a shortlist of priority species considering life-histories, habitat requirements, disturbance in populations caused by the habitat changes associated with the Nova Kakhovka Dam failure, and recommendations on recovery strategies.
- **Confidence in results:** The results would be of high confidence given that the ecologies of species of high conservation and commercial interest are well described. Uncertainty will be associated with future habitat constructs, although this could be addressed by including multiple future recovery scenarios.
- **Resulting messages:** detailed species level analysis of impacts and recovery strategies to inform prioritisation of future monitoring and remediation efforts.
- **Relevance to impact assessment and disaster recovery:** The proposed work would deliver detailed recommendations on the surveillance and long-term monitoring programmes necessary to quantify impacts on wider biodiversity. Monitoring programmes are established, for example, through the European Water Framework Directive, to assess water quality and ecological status generally. However, given the high number of endemic/rare and threatened

species, effort should be given to establishing species specific recovery plans. A biodiversity recovery strategy should be developed by an international expert group to inform prioritisation of future monitoring and remediation efforts. This may need to consider increasing capacity in Ukraine for ecological and pollutant monitoring as well as habitat improvement and the installation and placement of nature-based solutions to support recovery in large ecosystems, in line with the Transboundary Nature of the Dnipro River Basin.

5.3.10 Topic 10: Extending risk analysis from 'plausible' to 'realised' risk assessment

The assessment of risk on ecosystems and species is based here on expert judgement and so represents plausible risk. However, should further time allow further development and utilisation of products from this report, and where data are available through third parties, for example, through a bi-lateral agreement with Ukrainian data providers, it will be possible to use spatial data to increase the confidence of the risk assessment approach. For example, HR Wallingford hydrological models can be used to identify those regions subject to high flow where scouring and the wholesale destruction of habitats may have occurred, while the mapping of the spatial location of infrastructure (currently controlled by Ukrainian authorities) can be used to identify areas where major chemical releases are possible that may have contaminated receiving ecosystems in the vicinity. Understanding of the persistence of the hazard (potential at a detailed level for some hazards such as chemical pollution) can be used to assess whether the particular risk will act only transiently or will provide long-term impacts. For example, the stranding of some species may initially reduce some populations, but recovery may be feasible for rapidly reproducing species, similarly some chemical pollutants will be relatively quickly broken down, whereas others will persist.

- **Deliverables:** Spatial analysis at finer scale on areas of high impacts, including pollutant and sediment loading, habitat disturbance zones etc. Prioritisation of remediation measures around zones of high impact.
- **Confidence in results:** The results would be high level, but with a high degree of confidence, especially if suitable calibration data could be obtained through ground monitoring.
- **Resulting messages:** detailed habitat level analysis of risk to inform prioritisation of future monitoring and remediation efforts.
- **Relevance to impact assessment and disaster recovery:** The proposed work would further develop the approach taken here to establish a realised risk assessment allowing prioritisation for inclusion of habitats within immediate and

longer-term recovery action plans. This will require access to in situ and remotely sensed surveillance data, including on species distribution, pollutant concentrations and exposure levels, and recovery prospects in the context of mitigation scenarios. Persistence and extent of the hazards identified in this report is a clear knowledge gap that would be addressed in this work.

5.4 List of potential impacts discounted for future analysis by this project

5.4.1 Further breaching of Nova Kakhovka Dam

Images show a breach of a large section of the Nova Kakhovka Dam. Now that the level in the reservoir has reduced significantly, the forces on the remaining sections of the dam have reduced also, reducing the risk of further breaching. Despite this reduced risk, further breaching cannot be ruled out. For example, the rapid drawdown of water level in the reservoir could have triggered slips in the upstream slopes of the embankment sections.

Detailed information, which is unlikely to be made available in the timescales for this study, is required to make any assessment of further breaching.

5.4.2 Hydropower operations

The destruction of the dam has also affected its capability to generate electricity. Assessing the resilience of the system to cope with this loss of supply would require additional expertise.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX 1

Metadatabase of all major datasets used across components

Table A1.1. Metadata list including all major datasets used across project components.

ID	Name	URL	Licence
1	OpenStreetMap - Ukraine snapshot	http://download.geofabrik.de/europe.html	Open
2	Copernicus Global Land Cover	https://lcviewer.vito.be/download	Open
3	Ukraine Ramsar polygons	https://github.com/darsvid/ramsar_sites	Open
4	Ukraine population estimates	https://data.humdata.org/dataset/gridded-population-estimates-for-ukraine-using-un-cod-ps-estimates-2020-version-1-0	Open
5	Ukraine national / sub-national boundaries	https://data.humdata.org/dataset/cod-ab-ukr?	Open
6	HydroWASTE database	https://www.hydrosheds.org/products/hydrowaste	Open
7	Ramsar site data	https://rsis.ramsar.org/	Open
8	UNOSAT	https://www.unosat.org/products/3618	Open
9	World Database of Protected Areas	Explore the World's Protected Areas (protectedplanet.net)	Open (non-commercial)
10	GBIF	GBIF	Open
11	Global map of terrestrial habitat types	A global map of terrestrial habitat types Zenodo	Open
12	World Terrestrial Ecosystems (WTE) 2020	World Terrestrial Ecosystems (WTE) 2020 - ScienceBase-Catalog	Open
13	Kakhovka data	digitised / from OSM	Open
14	WorldCover	https://viewer.esa-worldcover.org/worldcover/?language=en&bbox=-337.5,-84.67351256610523,337.5,84.67351256610525&overlay=false&bgLayer=OSM&date=2023-06-13&layer=WORLDCOVER_2021_MAP	Open

15	Ukraine Waste Water Treatment Works	https://datacatalog.worldbank.org/search/dataset/0061361/Ukraine---Waste-water-treatment-plants	Open
16	Emerald Network sites database	Emerald Network data - the Pan-European network of protected sites — European Environment Agency (europa.eu)	Open
17	EUNIS Habitats	https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/data/eunis-habitat-classification-1	Open
18	EMODNet Seabed Habitats	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/	Open/mixed
19	Emerald Network interactive map	https://interecocentre.weebly.com/result-emerald-network-of-ukraine.html	Open
20	GLO-30 DTM	https://portal.opentopography.org/raster?opentopoID=OTSDEM.032021.4326.3	Copyrighted / mixed
21	HRW Hydraulic Model outputs	N/A	Project use
22	Landfills in Kherson Oblast	https://help.khoda.gov.ua/index.html	Unknown
23	Collated pollution dataset	N/A	Project use. From open/mixed data
24	European Red List – December 2017	https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/data/european-red-lists-7/european-red-list/european-red-list-csv-files	Open

APPENDIX 2

Land cover statistics for satellite-derived and modelled flood extents

Table A2.1. UNOSAT extent – WorldCover habitats.

CODE	Land Cover	Area m ²	Area Ha	% flooded area
10	Tree cover	104115800	10,411.58	16%
30	Grassland	109806300	10,980.63	17%
40	Cropland	27291600	2,729.16	4%
50	Built up	33420300	3,342.03	5%
60	Bare/sparse vegetation	777600	77.76	0%
80	Water bodies	43004300	4,300.43	7%
90	Herbaceous wetland	324989300	32,498.93	51%

Table A2.2. UNOSAT extent – IUCN habitats.

CODE	IUCNLevel	Area m ²	Area Ha	% flooded area
104	1.4. Forest – Temperate	36070000	3,607.00	6%
305	3.5. Shrubland – Subtropical/tropical dry	38970000	3,897.00	6%
404	4.4. Grassland – Temperate	1.02E+08	10,178.00	16%
500	5. Wetlands (inland)	3.23E+08	32,348.00	51%
501	5.1. Wetlands (inland) – Permanent rivers/streams/creeks (includes waterfalls)	2270000	227.00	0%
502	5.2. Wetlands (inland) – Seasonal/intermittent/irregular rivers/streams/creeks	8040000	804.00	1%
505	5.5. Wetlands (inland) – Permanent freshwater lakes (over 8 ha)	820000	82.00	0%
507	5.7. Wetlands (inland) – Permanent freshwater marshes/pools (under 8 ha)	18610000	1,861.00	3%
1401	14.1 Arable Land	53320000	5,332.00	8%
1403	14.3 Plantations	17810000	1,781.00	3%
1405	14.5 Urban Areas	32660000	3,266.00	5%

Table A2.3. UNOSAT extent – World Terrestrial Ecosystems.

CODE	Ecosystem	Area m ²	Area Ha	% flooded area
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138	COOL_TEMPERATE_DRY_FOREST_ON_PLAINS	2.29E+08	22,900.00	44%
144	COOL_TEMPERATE_DRY_SHRUBLAND_ON_PLAINS	7500000	750.00	1%
145	COOL_TEMPERATE_DRY_CROPLAND_ON_PLAINS	1.72E+08	17,162.50	33%
151	COOL_TEMPERATE_DRY_SPARSELY_OR_NON_VEGETATED_ON_PLAINS	687500	68.75	0%
153	COOL_TEMPERATE_DRY_GRASSLAND_ON_PLAINS	79062500	7,906.25	15%
157	COOL_TEMPERATE_DRY_SETTLEMENT_ON_PLAINS	30250000	3,025.00	6%

Table A2.4. Modelled maximum extent – WorldCover habitats.

CODE	Land Cover	Area m ²	Area Ha	% flooded area
10	Tree cover	90684500	9,068.45	11%
30	Grassland	80206000	8,020.60	10%
40	Cropland	8247400	824.74	1%
50	Built up	28442500	2,844.25	3%
60	Bare/sparse vegetation	664200	66.42	0%
80	Water bodies	301798300	30,179.83	36%
90	Herbaceous wetland	326326200	32,632.62	39%

Table A2.5. Modelled maximum extent – IUCN habitats.

CODE	IUCNLevel	Area m ²	Area Ha	% flooded area
104	1.4. Forest – Temperate	34900000	3,490.00	5%
305	3.5. Shrubland – Subtropical/tropical dry	36260000	3,626.00	5%
404	4.4. Grassland – Temperate	78090000	7,809.00	11%
500	5. Wetlands (inland)	3.74E+08	37,364.00	55%
501	5.1. Wetlands (inland) – Permanent rivers/streams/creeks (includes waterfalls)	45920000	4,592.00	7%
502	5.2. Wetlands (inland) – Seasonal/intermittent/irregular rivers/streams/creeks	10440000	1,044.00	2%
505	5.5. Wetlands (inland) – Permanent freshwater lakes (over 8 ha)	9390000	939.00	1%
507	5.7. Wetlands (inland) – Permanent freshwater marshes/pools (under 8 ha)	32550000	3,255.00	5%
1401	14.1 Arable Land	30030000	3,003.00	4%
1403	14.3 Plantations	6710000	671.00	1%
1405	14.5 Urban Areas	26730000	2,673.00	4%

Table A2.6. Modelled maximum extent – World Terrestrial Ecosystems.

CODE	Ecosystem	Area m ²	Area Ha	% flooded area
138	COOL_TEMPERATE_DRY_FOREST_ON_PLAINS	224937500	22,493.75	49%
144	COOL_TEMPERATE_DRY_SHRUBLAND_ON_PLAINS	7187500	718.75	2%
145	COOL_TEMPERATE_DRY_CROPLAND_ON_PLAINS	133625000	13,362.50	29%
151	COOL_TEMPERATE_DRY_SPARSELY_OR_NON_VEGETATED_ON_PLAINS	625000	62.50	0%
153	COOL_TEMPERATE_DRY_GRASSLAND_ON_PLAINS	72500000	7,250.00	16%
157	COOL_TEMPERATE_DRY_SETTLEMENT_ON_PLAINS	23562500	2,356.25	5%

APPENDIX 3

Species counts from the analysis of data from the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF), harmonised with European Red List species and intersected with the pre-flood water extents and predicted flood extent.

Summary of the number of protected species within the areas of interest. This table has been compiled using occurrence record data, dated from 1960 onwards, sourced from GBIF (GBIF.org (16 June 2023) GBIF Occurrence Download <https://doi.org/10.15468/dl.zpnsch>). Notes on use of these data:

- Values in the row 'Total', are less than the sums of the columns and rows in each section. This is because species may be present on both the European Red List and the Red Data Book of Ukraine, be present in multiple affected areas, or may use more than one ecosystem type.
- Numbers in brackets relate to the number of species as listed on the European Red List and Red Book Data of Ukraine. When working with species data from multiple sources, the taxon names need to be harmonised. In some cases, this results in multiple species on a list from one source being considered as single species on a list compiled by another source. Here, where this has occurred, and where the multiple species were assessed with different levels of concern or population trend, the 'worst case' assessment and/or trend has been selected.
- It has not yet been possible for us to harmonise all the species on the European Red List and Red Book Data of Ukraine to species within GBIF. The numbers in this table are therefore likely to be a conservative assessment of the number of protected species in the areas of interest.

Table A3.1. Species counts from the analysis of data from the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF).

	Combined extent	Pre-flood river extent	Maximum flood extent	Reservoir extent (pre-flood)
Total	581	267	427	163
European Red List	542 (567)	258	402	150
European Red List Status				
Extinct	1	0	1	1
Extinct in the Wild	0	0	0	0
Regionally Extinct	0	0	0	0
Critically Endangered	0	0	0	0
Endangered	6	5	3	1

Vulnerable	22	17	8	11
Near Threatened	19	9	11	10
Least Concern	484	224	373	126
Data Deficient	7	1	5	1
Not Applicable	3	2	1	0
European Red List Trend				
Decreasing	103	64	66	35
Stable	251	87	219	45
Increasing	70	46	44	31
Unknown	118	61	73	39
Red Data Book of Ukraine	135 (142)	58	75	72
Red Data Book of Ukraine Status				
Extinct	0	0	0	0
Extinct in Wild	0	0	0	0
Endangered	20	14	9	8
Vulnerable	66	27	39	37
Rare	37	14	16	24
Unvalued	9	1	8	3
Insufficiently Known	3	2	3	0
Ecosystem type				
Marine	95	82	40	29
Terrestrial	358	139	278	121
Freshwater	269	153	198	71
Taxonomic Class				
Amphibia	7	3	7	1
Aves	207	165	122	98
Bivalvia	4	3	2	0
Clitellata	1	0	1	0
Gastropoda	11	5	7	1
Insecta	83	8	64	24
Lecanoromycetes	3	2	3	0
Liliopsida	58	11	57	5
Magnoliopsida	126	27	121	4
Malacostraca	2	2	2	0
Mammalia	32	10	26	11
Polypodiopsida	4	3	3	0
Squamata	9	4	6	7
Teleostei	34	24	6	12

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